

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials

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D6.4: Report on Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities – Update 2

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the second updated version of the “Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities Report” of the VIBES project, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. The main objective of VIBES is to develop and demonstrate a new, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

With reference to the initial report and the first update elaborated in D6.2. and D6.3 respectively, this document describes the overall communication and dissemination strategy, the means and channels for communication and dissemination, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and the partners’ responsibilities in this respect. It includes specific communication, dissemination and training activities that have been and will be carried out by the VIBES consortium members, in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results.

The report outlines:

- **Why and what to disseminate:** the rationale of the project communication and dissemination strategy as well as the basic project-related information that has been and will be conveyed throughout the project are presented in Chapter 2.
- **To whom:** the key stakeholder groups that serve as the main audiences for the project’s communication and dissemination campaign are also presented in Chapter 2.
- **By what means:** all the means and channels that have been and will be used by project partners in order to successfully implement the communication, dissemination and training activities, are included in Chapters 3, 4 and 5 respectively.
- **When:** a time frame to ensure that the timing of the communication, dissemination and training activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project, is provided in Chapter 6.
- **Monitoring of the process:** the indicators to measure success on the communication, dissemination and training actions, enabling partners to refine efforts and actions over the course of the project, have been updated and they are specified in Chapter 7.

A third and final version of the “Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities Report” is foreseen in the 48th month of the project.

1. Introduction

VIBES aims to be a success story of collaboration among science, innovation and industrial entities from different countries to improve European Citizens' wellbeing. Therefore, to communicate this story is of paramount importance to maximize project results and multiply the impact in European society.

The main aim of VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training Plan is to provide the communication, dissemination and training strategy of the project. It has been updated and will be implemented during and after the project. Effective communication, dissemination and training activities have been and will be carried out, following a good communication and dissemination strategy that will guarantee:

- Addressing audiences beyond the action's own community (including the media and the public).
- Objectives clearly defined.
- Creative and expert people involved on them to achieve highest impact.

The current communication, dissemination and training report is the second updated version of the initial plan, assisting partners in designing and implementing their publicity, communication and engagement activities, within the framework of the project. It includes guidelines that can help achieve maximum visibility, so as to pave the way for a successful market uptake of the VIBES results. However, this report and its guidelines are subject to modifications and updates in line with the project progress and the experience that will be gained through the various project activities. As such, the communication, awareness raising and dissemination strategy that is presented in this report is not static. It is a living document that will be continuously reviewed in specific time intervals to account for any challenge or opportunity that may arise. A final version of the Communication, Dissemination and Training activities report is foreseen to be submitted in the 48th month of the project.

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

The objective of the Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities report is to target different audiences to create a European Identity, strengthening European Industry and building European Bridges. The main goals are:

1. To raise European citizens' awareness about cooperative research & innovation projects as the way to meet social challenges.
2. To facilitate the quick acceptance of breaking-edge technologies and innovative services within European industry.
3. To promote new, integrated business models, combining multi-criteria and multi-sectoral approach among decision-makers.

Therefore, clear messages have been and will be part of the VIBES story to face the concerns of European audiences reaching at least 100,000 citizens, 1,500 EU industries (at different levels, including technicians) in interconnected sectors and 500 decision makers (public such as legal entities and private such as company directors and business developers).

VIBES stems from cooperation within a European consortium between organisations based in different EU countries allowing to achieve better results, which would have otherwise been impossible. The project will validate a better use of resources to demonstrate the high potential of the Circular Economy with forward-looking climate change policies. This validation will be based on a technology evolution through scientific excellence (a first cost-effective recycling technology, based on the development of smart Bio-based materials, applied for the first time to thermoset composites), which will equip the Chemical Industry to make Europe a stronger global actor. In addition, the VIBES approach will wide open the door to the manufacturing industry to design and produce enhanced components to boost jobs, growth and investment at European level. Finally, the inter-sectoral relationships as well as the project's shared objectives will influence the different decision makers, contributing to competitiveness and helping to meet social challenges.

The VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training plan guides the strategies that set the key messages that should be sent from the partnership as well as the target audience, including gender balance aspects. The strategies focus on target sectors related to the VIBES approach: composite materials, polymers, chemicals, logistics and transport, aeronautical, naval, energy and construction sectors among the main ones. To maximise the interest of the VIBES stakeholders, impact multipliers at the local, regional, national, European and global levels have been used (for instance, by taking advantage of networking with other identified BBI/CBE and H2020/Horizon Europe projects, BIC and BBI/CBE channels). In addition, for the project's communication and dissemination activities, the consortium has identified media (press, magazines, digital media channels, thematic blogs, etc.) and events such as meetings, conferences, trade-fairs, workshops, training days, info-days, which are thematically close to the project. Moreover, a training plan has been aligned with the dissemination strategy with the aim of providing knowledge and skills to potential industrial collaborators and stakeholders for the envisaged new business and to science student profiles, in order to create a breeding ground of new talent for the creation of future jobs aligned with the new social and industrial needs.

1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables

This report serves to present the impact on communication and dissemination that the project is having in different areas. This deliverable includes the communication and dissemination activities implemented or foreseen in Task 6.2 "Communication Implementation" and Task 6.3 "Dissemination Implementation" as well as the workshops, courses and training foreseen in Task 6.4 "Training Implementation". The Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities is a horizontal action and the input for all relevant activities comes from the results and deliverables of all the other project work packages that include research, validation, pilot implementation and innovation actions.

As already mentioned above, the final update of this report includes deliverable D6.5 in month 48 at the end of the project, compiling all the activities carried out in the field of communication, dissemination and training.

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

With the above in mind, this updated version of the Communication, Dissemination and Training activities report, includes the updated VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training Strategy and Plan as well as the corresponding activities implemented until now, structured in 8 distinct chapters, as follows:

Chapter 1 - Introduction: it provides information about the scope of the report, its structure and its relationship with other activities and deliverables.

Chapter 2 - Communication and Dissemination Strategy: it defines and updates, where necessary, the strategy for dissemination and communication activities by outlining the objectives, the target audiences, with reference to the Stakeholders Board and synergies with other projects and initiatives, the key messages, the key assets of VIBES, the partners' role and responsibilities and the gender dimension.

Chapter 3 - Communication Means and Channels: it presents the different means and channels for carrying out the communication activities of the project, including the VIBES visual identity and promotional material, VIBES website and social media accounts, e-newsletters and press kit, participation in fairs and info-days and the Layman's report at the end of the project.

Chapter 4 - Dissemination Means and Channels: it presents the different means and channels for carrying out the dissemination activities of the project, including publications to scientific journals, participation in scientific conferences and events, organisation of events, such as forums, roundtables, workshops and final conference.

Chapter 5 - Training Programme: it describes the training strategy and activities that take place during the project to spread the idea of VIBES to younger generations of scientists and to industrial professionals.

Chapter 6 – Time Frame of Communication, Dissemination and Training activities: it provides the time frame of the communication, dissemination and training activities.

Chapter 7 - Performance Indicators, Monitoring and Reporting: it presents the way of monitoring and reporting the communication, dissemination and training activities, according to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set for those activities.

Chapter 8 - Conclusions: it summarises the conclusions of the updated Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities, as well as the way forward.

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overview and Objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of VIBES outlines the strategy that has been and will be followed for every communication, dissemination and training activity implemented or foreseen for the entire project duration. For that reason, it is a document that is largely connected with all the activities of the project's workplan.

The Communication and Dissemination strategy mostly aims to enable a wide reach and to contribute to a positive impact of the project, both exploiting the knowledge within the consortium and transferring the gained knowledge further to interested stakeholders. This strategy defines clear guidelines for all the dissemination and communication activities, which have been and will be carried out throughout the project.

The VIBES communication and dissemination strategy can be summed up into the following main objectives:

- Promote the project's concept, activities, and events to interested target groups and stakeholders.
- Enhance the awareness of the project's goals and assets.
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities.
- Encourage participation in relevant conferences and other events.
- Disseminate the project's results and gained knowledge to the public.
- Establish liaisons and synergies with other relevant initiatives.
- Facilitate market uptake of the project's results.
- Define partners' responsibilities in communication and dissemination activities.
- Organise training courses and workshops so that the ideas and outcomes of VIBES will be further developed by younger generations of scientists and industrial professionals.

To ensure a successful outcome of the objectives mentioned above, the VIBES communication and dissemination strategy focuses on a practical and realistic plan including the appropriate means, channels and actions to spread the ideas of VIBES and engage the target audiences, but it also remains flexible and open to changes when necessary. The key element for a successful Communication and Dissemination Plan is a well-structured methodology based on **what we want to disseminate** (project assets), **to whom** (which target groups), **by what means** (press releases, social media, communication and dissemination tools, channels etc.), and **when to disseminate**. Keeping these in mind, the following steps emerge:

- Identify the project's aims and appropriate communication and dissemination channels to ensure maximum visibility.
- Identify the main target groups and appropriate communication and dissemination channels for each group.
- Identify the key messages and project's assets.
- Link communication and dissemination channels to each target group and define communication and dissemination tools and methods which will be used during the project.

- Establish the roles and responsibilities of the partners in executing and managing the project’s communication and dissemination activities.
- Determine the stages of the communication and dissemination activities and overall timeline.
- Monitor key communication and dissemination indicators and adjust when necessary.

2.2 Target Audiences, Key Messages and Key Assets

2.2.1 The VIBES Target Audiences

All communication and dissemination activities contribute to the overall aim of facilitating the widespread adoption of VIBES results, thus maximising the project’s impact. Therefore, it is essential to clearly specify the VIBES target audiences.

The stakeholder groups that are illustrated in the following table have been identified as relevant to the VIBES project and, thus, represent the target audiences of the current communication and dissemination strategy.

Table 1. VIBES stakeholder groups and sub-groups

Group	Sub-group
Industrial developers	Thermoset composite material developers
	Composite recyclers
Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users	Aeronautical
	Naval
	Construction
	Energy
	Waste management
	Logistics
	Transport
Technology/ Innovation Experts	Academics and/or Researchers
	Technology and/or Innovation consultants
Impact multipliers	Policy makers
	Media/ journalists or bloggers

Group	Sub-group
	Relevant projects or initiatives

The identified stakeholder groups of the VIBES project are described below in more detail:

- **Industrial Developers:** industries that develop composite materials and/ or technologies for their recycling (thermoset composite material developers, composite recyclers).
- **Industrial Users:**
 - **Industrial Converters:** industries that manufacture equipment or build infrastructure, which includes parts made of composite materials, such as the aeronautical industry, the naval or shipbuilding industry, the construction and energy industries.
 - **Industrial Dismantlers:** companies that dismantle industrial facilities or infrastructure and are responsible for their waste management and disposal.
 - **Industrial End-users:** industries that use and/ or maintain equipment or infrastructure with parts made of composite materials, such as the transportation (airports, railway, shipping) and logistics sectors.
- **Academic Community:** researchers at universities and other research organisations working in the fields of materials science and engineering, composites, chemistry, chemical engineering, biotechnology, recycling technologies, waste management, as well as other relevant disciplines (e.g. environmental sciences, social sciences, technical fields).
- **Technology and/or Innovation consultants:** organisations or individuals with expertise in technological and/ or commercial aspects of innovative technologies regarding sustainability and the circular economy.
- **Policy Makers:** decision-makers, EU and national level stakeholders, as well as the relevant standardisation and certification authorities, playing a key role in policy design, adoption and implementation, in the fields of the environment, waste management and circular economy.
- **Media/ Journalists or bloggers:** press or individual writers, specialised in relevant topics, such as new technologies and bioeconomy, waste management, circular economy.
- **Relevant projects or initiatives:** complementary EU actions and national or regional projects and initiatives within the EU bioeconomy and circular economy ecosystem (see section 2.2.3)

2.2.2 The VIBES Stakeholders Board

The VIBES Stakeholders Board (SB) includes individuals, either independent or representing organisations, who are external to the consortium partners. It is formed by a minimum number of 10 representatives, consisting of experts and representatives of various stakeholder groups in the whole value chain of VIBES, with activity in both local and European settings.

The members of the Stakeholders Board are strategically involved in key stages of the project to contribute with their expertise and represent the views and interests of their stakeholder groups, in order to better guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy. They

collaborate in the project to effectively respond to market and social needs, give feedback and better guide decisions in the project. They are industry-led, while fostering public and private collaboration.

The Stakeholders Board completes the whole value chain together with consortium partner members and is chaired by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN representative). Specific dissemination activities with the Stakeholders Board, including demonstration workshops and roundtables, will take place (see sections 4.3.2 and 4.3.3) to share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept effectively.

Partners nominate individuals belonging to relevant stakeholder groups after initially contacting them informally, with the aim to be invited to participate in the Stakeholders Board.

After having received the initial informal interest and consent of the nominated individuals, the partners provided the following information to the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PAN), using an EXCEL file named “Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders” (see Annex 1):

- Stakeholder group/ sub-group that the nominated person belongs to (either chosen from the groups listed in the above Table 1 or by specifying another group/ sub-group)
- Contact name and gender of the nominated person
- Contact email
- Organisation name and website (if applicable)
- Country
- Consortium partner (name/ organisation) that nominated them
- To be invited as Stakeholders Board member (yes/ no/ maybe)
- Any comments (i.e. specifying if they are member(s) of a relevant project or initiative, a relevant working group or cluster etc.)

Following their initial informal interest and consent, the nominated stakeholders were officially invited by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) to participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board by signing the “Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent Form” (Annex 2), after having read and agreed to the “Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference” (Annex 3) and the [VIBES Privacy Policy](#) (available on the VIBES website). The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) followed up the communication with the nominated stakeholders and included them in the VIBES Stakeholders Board after having received the signed Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent form. Those who did not provide the signed form are not considered members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

The following figures show details about the current composition of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

Figure 1. Number of VIBES Stakeholders Board members per stakeholder type

Figure 2. Number of VIBES Stakeholders Board members per country

Figure 3. Gender of VIBES Stakeholders Board members

2.2.3 Synergies with Other Projects and Initiatives

Synergies within the EU bioeconomy and circular economy ecosystem, as well as complementary EU actions and regional/ national projects and initiatives, have been pursued by all partners in the VIBES research domains and industry sectors, to facilitate knowledge exchange, gain mutual dissemination benefits and exploit potential co-operations.

The following Table presents an updated list of projects and initiatives that have been identified as being related to VIBES, some more closely than others.

Table 2. Projects/ initiatives related to VIBES

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
Horizon2020 Project	BIZENTE	A biocatalytic model of enzymatic degradation as a novel alternative to the end-of-life (landfill and incineration) of thermoset composites.
Horizon2020 Project	ECOXY	Bio-based, recyclable, re-shapable & repairable (3R) fibre reinforced thermoset composites.
Horizon2020 Project	polynSPIRE	Demonstration of innovative technologies towards a more efficient and sustainable plastic recycling
LIFE Project	LIFE RECYSITE	Demonstrating recyclability and reuse of a new generation of high-performance fibre-reinforced thermoset composites from renewable resources (bio-waste).
Horizon2020 Project	HELACS	Holistic processes for the cost-effective and sustainable management of End of Life of Aircraft Composite Structures.
	BAMCO	Design of bio-composites from bamboo fibres and biobased resins, either thermoplastic or thermosets.
Horizon2020Project	LIBRE	Development and demonstration of the feasibility of lignin-based carbon fibre materials for application in energy and automotive sectors.
European Association	SPIRE	European Association, bringing together cement, ceramics, chemicals, engineering, minerals and ores, non-ferrous metals, pulp and paper, refining, steel and water sectors, several being world-leading

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
		sectors operating from Europe.
Horizon Europe Project	CUBIC	Improving the circularity of complex plastic multi-material composites using novel biobased materials in B2B semi-finished products.
Horizon Europe Project	BIO UPTAKE	Ensure a sustainable uptake (increase the use in a 39%) of bioplastic composites through boosting a twin green and digital transformation in the European manufacturing industry.
Horizon Europe Project	EoLO-HUBs	Recovering glass and carbon fibre from wind turbine blades at the end of their useful lives and creating a knowledge hub to facilitate the recycling.
European Network	Clean Aviation	EU's leading research and innovation programme for transforming aviation towards a sustainable, climate-neutral future; an institutionalised European Partnership for Clean Aviation under Horizon Europe; building on the success of Clean Sky and Clean Sky 2.
European Network	2Zero	A co-programmed Partnership funded under the Horizon Europe programme and aiming at accelerating the transition towards zero tailpipe emission road mobility across Europe; promoting the delivery of green vehicles and mobility system solutions in Europe; building upon the successes of the European Green Cars Initiative (EGCI: 2009-2013) and the European Green Vehicles Initiative (EGVI: 2014-2020).
European Network	A.SPIRE/ P4Planet	Committed to manage and implement the Processes4Planet co-programmed Partnership. It represents innovative process industries, 20% of the total European manufacturing sector in employment and turnover, and more than 170 industrial and research process stakeholders from over a dozen countries spread throughout Europe. A.SPIRE brings together cement, ceramics, chemicals, engineering, minerals and ores, non-ferrous metals, pulp and

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
		<p>paper, refining, steel and water sectors, several being world-leading sectors operating from Europe. The Processes4Planet (P4Planet) Partnership aim is to transform the European process industries to achieve circularity and overall climate neutrality at the EU level by 2050 while enhancing their global competitiveness. SPIRE has been the contractual Public-Private Partnership active between 2014 and 2020 and dedicated to innovation in resource and energy efficiency enabled by the process industries. The cPPP has been launched under the Horizon 2020 Programme by A.SPIRE - as the private entity - and the European Commission.</p>

The actions required to create synergies with relevant projects and initiatives are coordinated by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager with support from the rest of the consortium partners.

Synergies may include participation in events of similar projects and initiatives, dissemination of VIBES promotional material in events of similar projects and initiatives, invitations to participate in VIBES events, exchange of news through each other’s channels, inclusion of the project’s website and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects and initiatives, provision of feedback in each project’s activities, etc.

Synergies with certain projects also include co-organisation of specific dissemination events, such as the demonstration workshops that have been organised in collaboration with some of the projects and initiatives mentioned in Table 2, as described in Chapter 4, section 4.3.2.

2.2.4 The VIBES Key Messages

It is very important for the VIBES Communication and Dissemination Strategy to define the fundamental messages of the project that will be communicated to the target audiences. A crucial point of the decided key messages is that they give a clear image of the project’s vision, but they are also tailored depending on the needs of each target group (e.g. industrial developers and industrial users who would be interested in the use of the VIBES developed materials and recycling technology, academics and scientists who would be interested in the scientific methods and results of VIBES and policy makers, the media and the general public, who are concerned about a greener economy and the protection of the environment.)

Although these messages are specified as the project progresses, based on the actual data and outcomes and the milestones achieved, a list of the main key messages of the project that have been and will be communicated to each stakeholder group, including the means used, is provided in the following Table as a point of reference.

Table 3. Key messages and means used for VIBES targeted stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Group	Key Messages	Means
<p>Industry (developers and users)</p>	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves properties of thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, leading to reduced environmental impact, combined with higher cost-effectiveness and increased profitability. • Contributes to reduced use of primary materials and landfilling. • Produces added-value products for the circular economy. • Facilitates the use of thermoset composite materials in industrial sectors without restrictions or environmental concerns. • Provides new knowledge for the European Industry on the circular economy for thermoset composite materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Leaflets • Infographic • Articles in industry magazines • Presentations in conferences, fairs and info-days • COMPOSIFORUM international events • Demonstration workshops • Research workshops for researchers and technicians • Roundtables • Layman’s report • Final conference
<p>Academic and research community</p>	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shares new knowledge and data on bio-based thermoset composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties. • Shares new knowledge and data on recycling technology based on green pre-treatments. • Provides new knowledge and skills for European students in materials science, engineering and chemical fields, for new arising demand in technical jobs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Scientific publications • Presentations in scientific conferences/ forums • COMPOSIFORUM international event • Research workshops for researchers and technicians • Summer courses for younger generation of scientists • Final conference

Stakeholder Group	Key Messages	Means
Policy makers	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreases the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. Boosts jobs, growth and investments with forward-looking policies for climate change. Achieves better results through collaborative innovation, contributing to competitiveness and helping meet social challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentations in conferences, fairs and info-days COMPOSIFORUM international event Roundtables Layman’s report Final conference
Press General public	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrates an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling solution. Returns products obtained from recycling process to the market. Boosts jobs, growth and investments with forward-looking policies for climate change. Provides new knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Project social media e-Newsletters Press releases and articles Digital media channels Promotional videos Layman’s report

Note that in order to fulfil the project’s ambitions and claims, the above concepts/ messages must be communicated in their entirety.

2.2.5 The VIBES Key Assets

The VIBES project has specific assets that can be of interest to different stakeholder groups and are disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective industrial users and nurture the ground for their post-project rollout. Although the VIBES assets are defined in parallel to the unfolding of the project activities, a preliminary list of core assets is shown in the following Table. This list will evolve and be completed in the course of the project.

Table 4. VIBES main exploitable assets and outcomes (preliminary list)

VIBES main assets and outcomes
The VIBES 100% Biobased Bonding Materials , specific for epoxy, vinylester and polyester.
The VIBES 100% biobased resins and fibres to be used as new thermoset composite components.
The VIBES new technology for thermoset composites with intrinsic recycling properties.

VIBES main assets and outcomes
The VIBES new green recycling technology , resolving thermoset composites' end-of-life
The VIBES valorised resins (monomers/oligomers) and fibres , recovered from the recycling process, to be returned to the market as new feedstocks for different chemicals or building blocks and by upcycling into new industrial products.
The VIBES industry-oriented protocols and manuals of new developed solutions, to be used for certification and authorisation of use.
The VIBES training course for industrial professionals on the circular economy for thermoset composites, to further develop the ideas and outcomes of VIBES.
The VIBES summer master classes for students on green composites, providing new knowledge and skills to the younger generation of scientists and engineers.
The VIBES brand and community of stakeholders , comprised of industrial developers and users of thermoset composite materials, the corresponding academic and research community, relevant technology & innovation experts, as well as policy makers, facilitating the dissemination and market uptake of VIBES results.

2.3 Role and Responsibilities

In order to achieve the aims and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, all members of the project consortium play a key role during VIBES communication and dissemination activities. Partners' contribution is a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones and progress will either involve communication and dissemination activities and engagement or turn into communication and dissemination assets. Furthermore, partners help with the online presence of VIBES by providing content for the project news published on the website and the project's Social Media accounts. This contribution can be anything, from a Twitter post to an article reflecting on a VIBES dissemination activity, with the goal of creating a constant flow of content regarding project's actions.

Finally, partners are welcome to pursue the widest possible exposure of the project through their participation in relevant events/conferences, articles and publications in online/offline sources of information (e.g. websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.).

2.4 The Gender Dimension

The gender dimension has been integrated into the communication, dissemination and training strategy, including the establishment and monitoring of relevant indicators (see Table 10). Specific targets for the participation of women in certain communication, dissemination and training activities have been set, in order to guarantee gender balance and equality.

In particular, the gender dimension has been and will be taken into consideration during the process of communicating with or selecting members and participants in various activities and events, as follows:

- In general, whenever possible, targeting communication and dissemination activities more intensely towards stakeholder groups that are represented by a fair number of female members.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when selecting members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board; currently, at least 50% of its members are female (see figure 3 in section 2.2.2).
- Taking the gender aspect into account when approaching academics and researchers, technicians, industrial professionals, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders, in order to invite them to participate in the project's relevant events (i.e. forums, workshops, roundtables, training programme and final conference); it is envisaged that at least 30% of the participants in such events will be female.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when selecting the students for the summer training courses of the VIBES training programme, in which at least 30% of students are expected to be female.

3. Communication Means and Channels

Communication activities aim at increasing the public visibility of the project and its results using accessible language and suitable means and channels.

3.1 Visual Identity and Promotional Package

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) is in charge of the preparation of VIBES visual identity and the graphic design and content of the digital and printable promotional material of VIBES.

The promotional material of the project is mainly used at the project's events, external events where partners participate in and in the everyday publicity of the project.

3.1.1 Logo

By the end of the second month of the project, a project logo and visual identity were developed, in order to satisfy the visual and graphic requirements of the project. To achieve maximum visibility, the logo has the capability to make the project recognisable and will form the basis for the design of all the promotional material, which will be used for the different promotional and communication materials (e.g. leaflets, posters, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.).

The logo is represented on a friendly rounded font. The design involves the letter V which consists of 2 leaves; the green leaf refers to Green Solution and the purple leaf refers to Chemistry Innovation. The tag line connects the idea of Green Economy with that of Chemistry Innovation.

The logo colours (i.e. dark purple: #3C0F4B R: 60 / G: 15 / B:75 and light green: #23C887 R: 35 / G: 200 / B:135) are the colours of the project and should be used whenever possible to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project.

The designed logo of VIBES, presented below with and without tag line, was adopted in agreement with all project partners.

Figure 4. VIBES logo with tag line

Figure 5. VIBES logo without tag line

Figure 6. The color codes of VIBES logo

In addition to the VIBES project logo, in any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc. produced in the frame of the project, the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) logo, combined with the Bio-based Industries Consortium logo and the Horizon2020 logo, has been and will be shown.

Figure 7. The combined logo of Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking, Bio-based Industries Consortium and Horizon2020

The above combined logo will always be accompanied by the following statement: “This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium”.

3.1.2 Leaflets

Leaflets are important tools to support the communication and dissemination activities of VIBES project to attract the interest of stakeholders from the various target audiences.

By the end of the third month of the project, the first leaflet was produced in electronic and printable formats. It introduces the VIBES aim and goals, the project phases, the expected results and benefits.

A second leaflet summarising all project's achievements will be produced in electronic and printable formats at the mid-end of the project so it can be distributed through partners' networks and at relevant events.

The leaflets also provide information about the consortium partners and the type of stakeholders involved, together with contact and website details and acknowledge the funding that the project receives through the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under European Union's Horizon 2020 programme. The leaflets will be available in downloadable electronic format on the VIBES website. Furthermore, specifications on how to produce hard copies of the printable format of the leaflet will be given to all partners. Each partner will be responsible to produce the necessary number of printed copies of the leaflets to be available for distribution at various events that will be organised in the frame of the project but also in external events, which partners will participate in.

The first leaflet of the project is illustrated below. The recommended specifications for producing hard copies of the printable format of the leaflet are as follows:

- Tri-Fold
- Dimensions: 14X29cm (42X29cm open)
- Paper: Velvet 250gr
- Mat Varnish

Figure 8. The first leaflet of VIBES

Aim

Develop and demonstrate an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, with the aim of decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

Project Goals

Design and develop at least three 100% biobased bonding materials (BBM) for thermoset composites with tailored debonding functionalities.

- Design and develop at least three 100% biobased thermoset composite materials.
- Validate the thermoset composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties for optimum performance / cost ratio, in three high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.
- Design and implement a green recycling technology at pilot semi-industrial environment to separate and valorise the composite components as new feedstocks for the development of new products.
- Assess the life cycle impact of the developed products from environmental, social and economic point of view.
- Develop an exploitation & IPR strategy for Key Exploitable Results.
- Develop a Business Plan to demonstrate the commercial potential of the developed solution and describe how this potential will be realised.
- Inform, promote, communicate and disseminate the project objectives, activities and results; engage stakeholders to create synergies.
- Provide new knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

Stakeholders

The VIBES project covers the whole composites value chain by taking into account, apart from the consortium partners, the Stakeholders Board and interaction with other projects of Biobased Industries through communication and dissemination activities:

- Industrial developers: thermoset composite developers, composite recyclers.
- Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users: aeronautical, naval, construction and energy industries; waste management; logistics and transport.
- Technology & innovation experts: academic / researchers; technology and innovation consultants.
- Impact multipliers: policy makers; media / journalists or bloggers.

3.1.3 Infographic

To add to the communication promotional package available for the communication activities of VIBES project, an infographic was created by the end of the fifth month of the project. The infographic has the purpose of explaining the VIBES solution on recycling composites to a public audience and can be used in stands or booths. It has been produced in electronic and printable formats, following the same overall layout designed for the project, and it is also available for downloading from the VIBES website.

The infographic has been designed to be produced as a poster or as a roll up banner. The recommended specifications for producing hard copies of the printable formats of the infographic are as follows:

- Poster:
 - Dimensions: A3 (29.70X42cm) and A0 (84.10X11.89cm)
 - Paper: Velvet 200gr
- Roll Up banner:
 - Dimensions: 80X200cm
 - Paper: Velvet 200gr

Project Phases

Phase 1: Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)	Phase 2: Biobased Thermoset Composite Components	Phase 3: Inherent Recyclable Thermoset Composites	Phase 4: Recycling Technology Development	Phase 5: Sustainability and Commercial Exploitation
Three different approaches	Biobased substitutes for resins	Design and synthesis	Collection and direction to recycling	Sustainability and economical assessment
Exploring combinations and synergies	Biobased fibres and surface treatments	Technical validation tests	Handling, toxicity and safety evaluation	Aligning with Green Deal and climate neutral strategy
Upscaling best BBM	New fabrics for composite applications	Testing debonding treatments	Recycling technology design	Involvement of supply chain & EPR considerations
	Upscaling best composite components	Valorisation of recovered fractions	Pilot recycling plant	Exploitation & IPR management
		Upscaling into high added-value products		Building a business case
Phase 6: Communication, Dissemination and Training	Communication, dissemination and training plan.	Communication campaign and dissemination actions.	Stakeholders' engagement, creating synergies.	Providing knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

www.vibesproject.eu

Benefits

- Improved properties of thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, leading to reduced environmental impact, combined with higher cost-effectiveness and increased profitability.
- Reduced use of primary materials and landfilling.
- Use of thermoset composite materials in industrial sectors without restrictions or environmental concerns.
- New knowledge for the European Industry on the circular economy for thermoset composite materials.
- New knowledge and skills for European students in material science, engineering and chemical fields, for new arising demand in technical jobs.
- Increased jobs and turnover by promoting two new industrial sector interconnections in the newly created "Intrinsic Recyclable Thermoset Composites Value Chain":
 - Interconnection between waste management and biotechnology sectors.
 - Interconnection between thermoset composites and biotechnology sectors.

Figure 9. The infographic of VIBES in a poster form

Figure 10. The infographic of VIBES in a roll up form

3.1.4 Promotional Videos

By the end of the fifth month of the project, a [promotional video](#) was produced to raise awareness and to exploit viral effects. The video was uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and the project’s website and was shared on the other Social Media Accounts. This short video gives an overview of the project and its objectives, and it presents the main actions of the VIBES project.

A second promotional video will be produced at the end of the project, including the main project results and outcomes, and will be also uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and shared on the other Social Media Accounts.

Figure 11. The story board of the official VIBES promotional video

13 The introduction of VIBES project

← reducing the negative impact of their waste in the environment.

14 The VIBES new green technology

← It is based on the development of a new green technology...

15 The VIBES new green technology

← focused on the controlled separation...

16 The VIBES new green technology

← and recovery of compatible material components.

17 The VIBES new green technology

← by means of developing sustainable...

18 The VIBES new green technology

← bio-based bonding materials.

19 The aim of the new green technology

← The new cost-efficient and non-toxic recycling technology solutions...

20 The aim of the new green technology

← allow to decrease the amount of non biodegradable polymers sent to incineration...

21 The aim of the new green technology

← can be discharged to the environment and at least 40%.

22 The obtained products

← The products obtained from the recycling process will return to the market...

23 The obtained products

← by means of their reutilization as new products or as different elements in the building blocks...

24 The obtained products

← used for sporting new new industrial products.

25 The growth benefits

← benefits will be significant also in terms of growth increasing sales...

26 The growth benefits

← and customer by promoting new new industrial uses or components in the supply chain...

27 The growth benefits

← "The most Biodegradable Thermoset Composite Value Chain"

3.1.5 Document and Presentation Templates

With a view to design an easily recognisable graphical identity for the project, the following templates have been developed and updated:

- Presentation template in PowerPoint, that is used as a basis for the various presentations created during the project, either for internal or external communication.
- Document template in MSWord, that is used as a basis for the project deliverables and reports.
- Letterhead template in MSWord, that is used for communication with project stakeholders and other written communication about the project.

These templates are shown in Annex 4.

3.1.6 Image Galleries

Image galleries are used as visual promotional material in communication activities, for instance when posting news on the project website and social media or in project presentations and articles and the Layman’s report. The image galleries include the following types of images:

- Pictures of VIBES related technologies and products, processes, teams and facilities.
- Images using the VIBES visual identity and colours including short promotional text and/ or relevant icons, mainly to be used when posting news on the project website and social media.
- Pictures or screenshots of project meetings, mainly used when posting relevant news on social media.

A repository of images has been created, including pictures of relevant technologies and products, processes, teams and facilities, shared by several consortium partners. It is expected that during the course of the project, the consortium partners will continue to share relevant pictures of the various stages of the VIBES developed technologies and processes, showing the project progress.

Figure 12. Images of VIBES News

3.2 VIBES Website

The project website (www.vibesproject.eu) is a key communication tool to increase the project visibility and impact, presenting the progress of the project to wider audiences. The VIBES website was launched in the fourth month of the project and serves as the online platform for public and consortium communication. The structure and content of the website have been designed to ensure ease of use and clearly reports the project's concept and objectives but will also contain relevant information about its progress, with news and event announcements.

Q-PLAN is the partner responsible for the design, development, maintenance, and management of the website. Special attention has been paid to a type of website that is responsive and accessible via and compatible with a variety of devices, including mobile devices.

Besides the key information presented, the project website includes all publishable project's outcomes, promotional material, reports, publications, deliverables and further resources of interest. The website reflects the work happening in the context of VIBES. All partners are, hence, expected to contribute to the content development process with news and updates. The website regularly reports on project's activities,

internal and external events, findings, publishable outcomes, information about partners and similar projects/initiatives, as well as other news that are relevant to the project and its development.

The full structure and content of the VIBES website is presented in deliverable D6.1 “Project Website”. The website sitemap is illustrated below:

- Home page
- About:
 - Concept and objectives
 - Consortium partners
 - Stakeholders
 - Activities
- Resources:
 - Reports
 - Publications
 - Training material
 - Promotional material
 - Other links (relevant events, relevant projects)
- News & Events:
 - Project developments
 - Dissemination and training events
 - Newsletters
 - Press Releases
- Contact us
- Privacy Policy
- Private area (link to MSTeams collaborative space for VIBES)

The above-mentioned points constitute a baseline for the website. The content and information posted on the website is updated regularly, to be in line with the project’s requirements and progress. The URL for the website is www.vibesproject.eu and the contact email for the project is in line with it (info@vibesproject.eu).

Figure 13. Google analytics presenting the users (visitors) of the website

3.3 Social Media Accounts

The Social Media Accounts are valuable tools, which act as one of the main pillars to promote the project and its ongoing activities. More specifically, a Twitter account, a LinkedIn account and a Facebook account were launched during the first month of the project, whereas a YouTube account was created during the third month of the project, aiming to build an online community of supporters and followers that will continue to exist beyond the duration of the project.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) is responsible for the administration of VIBES social media accounts. However, all partners contribute by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile).
- Promoting the accounts in their networks.
- Suggesting relevant profiles that VIBES should connect with.
- Promoting posts and news through the social media accounts of their own organisations.

Table 5. VIBES social media accounts

Social Media Platform	Name of Account	URL
Twitter	@VIBESEU2	https://twitter.com/VIBESEU2
LinkedIn	vibes-project	https://www.linkedin.com/company/vibes-project/
Facebook	VIBESProject2021	https://www.facebook.com/VIBESProject2021
YouTube	VIBES Project	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCauYtwBy8V47hLdnpzROZ8Q

Twice per week, the project’s social media are updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from several organisations / associations that promote activities and technologies relevant to VIBES, news from related EU projects etc.

The YouTube channel has been updated, including the first promotional video of VIBES that was published online in the fifth month of the project and the VIBES Summer Course Video that was published in the twenty-eighth month of the project.

Screenshots of the VIBES presence on social media accompanied with analytics regarding the followers and the engagement (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube) are presented in Annex 5.

3.4 E-Newsletters

The project has committed to produce a bi-annual electronic newsletter (at least 8 in total), covering the activities developed every semester. The timing of the launch of each newsletter may be adapted to announce special events. The newsletter is distributed to the project’s target audience, including all those who subscribe to it via the project website, and it is also uploaded to the website. Moreover, the project has launched the addition of a LinkedIn Newsletter as a strategic action to enhance the dissemination of the VIBES newsletter. The newsletter summarises updates on the project’s developments and actions and

represents an alternative way to inform potential and/or existing followers with regards to the project's concepts. Furthermore, the newsletter is a way to attract and retain stakeholders that are not familiar with social media or people who are not interested enough during the initial phases of the project, in order to keep them connected and try to engage them at a later stage.

The newsletter issues are prepared by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager, with the contribution of all partners to specific content when necessary. Although the content of each newsletter issue is agreed upon in collaboration with project partners, the newsletter mainly includes the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the VIBES project
- Progress updates
- A project's news section including articles that describe the main activities carried out during the last six months
- A section dedicated to future developments (e.g. upcoming events)
- A section listing other relevant major events
- Other types of relevant articles

The final newsletter will be accompanied by a feedback questionnaire for recipients to indicate the level of impact on them from information on project progress, achievements and recommendations.

At this stage, five issues of the VIBES electronic newsletter have been published and disseminated, and they can be found on the project website in the [Newsletters](#) section. Indicatively, the last two issues of the VIBES e-newsletter are presented in Annexes 6 and 7.

3.5 Press Kit

3.5.1 Press Releases and Articles

At least six press releases will be produced on an ad-hoc basis, especially when achievements, progress and important actions are achieved or foreseen (i.e. an upcoming event). The press releases aim to inform stakeholders about the overall project actions and results, but they may also incorporate space for featuring specific stories related to project achievements in the form of short articles. General press releases will be developed, when necessary, targeting stakeholders at the EU level. Press releases may also be produced after each project meeting or prior to a project event with the purpose of attracting local media attention.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager is in charge of preparing each press release, but every partner is responsible for translating the press releases into their local language and communicate them to their local press or via their own digital channels (partners websites and/ or social media).

At this stage of the project, six press releases have been produced and published, available on the project website in the [Press Releases](#) section. The first press release was launched after the project kick-off meeting to announce the beginning of the project and introduce the project's goals and partners. The second press release was launched after the launch of the project website to attract the interest of stakeholders to visit the project website, subscribe to the electronic newsletter and follow VIBES on social media. The third press release was launched following the 1st year anniversary of the project, outlining the

project progress during the first year and the next steps. The fourth, fifth and sixth press releases were launched following the consortium project meeting referring to the project progress. Indicatively, the last two press releases of VIBES are presented in Annexes 8 and 9.

3.5.2 Digital media channels

In an effort to reach a wider audience and promote the innovative concepts of bioeconomy and circular economy, our project partners have been actively engaged in digital platforms for dissemination.

BCIRC showcased the project's impact in an episode of Energy Trends in the podcast broadcast on 28th March 2022 with the title "Circular economy: a paradigm that proposes rethinking the way we design, produce and consume". In the [podcast](#) Oriol Grau, head of BCIRC, debates with Edith Guedella, Head of the road and environment group at ACCIONA, Francisco Ruiz, Director of Business Consulting for NTT DATA and Iñigo Vegas, Director of the Cement Based Products Business Area at Tecnalia, about the new sustainable materials of the future, using the VIBES project as an example.

Furthermore, Teruel Airport (PLATA) generated a video in the platform INDUSTRY TALKS with the title [Sustainable Innovation in Aeronautic Sector](#), in which the VIBES project was introduced (see figure 14). That platform has 1660 subscribers, so its scope is very interesting for VIBES.

In addition to leveraging digital platforms, the project coordinator AITIIP shared insightful results of the VIBES project at [Veltha](#)'s LOOPS 3.0 second [webinar](#), titled "Composites for the Circular Economy: VIT meets VIBES," held on January 22, 2024. This activity demonstrates further our commitment to disseminating the project's advancements effectively.

Figure 14. Alejandro Ibrahim (PLATA) I-Talks

Figure 15. AITIIP at LOOPS webinar

3.6 Articles in Press and Industry Magazines

In order for the project to reach a broader audience and make the VIBES known to its industrial stakeholders who belong to a wide range of industries and services, the partners are encouraged to submit their findings as articles in relevant magazines, both locally and internationally.

The following Table lists the articles about VIBES that have been published in local press and industry magazines.

Table 6. Articles about VIBES in local press and industry magazines

Partner	Date	Name of magazine/newspaper	Type	Link
ULIM	19/06/02021	Limerick Leader	General	https://www.limerickleader.ie/news/news/642549/groundbreaking-research-at-ul-helps-develop-cheaper-and-more-sustainable-carbon-fibre.html
AITIIP	23/06/2021	Heraldo de Aragón	General	https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/aragon/2021/06/23/vibes-un-proyecto-europeo-que-busca-

Partner	Date	Name of magazine/ newspaper	Type	Link
				soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion-1501499.html
AITIIP	23/6/2021	Mundoplast	Plastic sector	https://mundoplast.com/proyecto-vibes-reciclar-compuestos-termoestables/
AITIIP	23/06/2021	InterEmpresas	Business, focused on technology	https://www.interempresas.net/Nautica/Articulos/354671-AITIIP-desarrollara-tecnologia-ecologica-reciclar-piezas-termoestables-aeronautica.html
AITIIP	24/06/2021	Química y Sociedad	Chemical sector	https://www.quimicaysociedad.org/aitiip-lidera-el-proyecto-vibes-que-desarrollara-una-tecnologia-ecologica-para-reciclar-piezas-termoestables-en-los-sectores-naval-aeronautico-y-construccion/
AITIIP	25/06/2021	Heraldo de Aragón	General	
AITIIP	26/06/2021	Retema	Environmental sector	https://www.retema.es/noticia/espana-lidera-un-proyecto-para-desarrollar-tecnologia-para-reciclar-compuestos-plasti-xKnJT
AITIIP	28/06/2021	Construible	Sustainable construction	https://www.construible.es/2021/06/28/vibes-desarrollara-tecnologia-ecologica-reciclar-polimeros-reutilizarlos-construccion
AITIIP	02/07/2021	Gestores de Recursos	Waste management	https://gestoresderesiduos.org/noticias/un-proyecto-europeo-con-participacion-espanola-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion

Partner	Date	Name of magazine/newspaper	Type	Link
AITIIP	04/07/2021	Aragón Digital	General	https://www.aragondigital.es/2021/07/04/el-centro-tecnologico-aitiip-lidera-un-proyecto-para-desarrollar-una-tecnologia-ecologica-de-reciclaje-de-piezas/
AITIIP	04/07/2021	Aragón Press	General	http://aragonpress.com/pages/notic/noticia.asp?notid=598423
AITIIP	07/07/2021	Diario de Teruel	General	https://www.diariodeteruel.es/teruel/el-aeropuerto-de-teruel-socio-en-un-proyecto-de-reciclaje-de-piezas-42551
DITF	26/07/2021	Dezeen	General	https://www.dezeen.com/2021/07/26/carbon-bio-based-carbon-fibres/
AITIIP	04/08/2021	Tecnología Circular	Circular economy, technology and innovation	https://www.tecnologiacircular.cl/2021/08/proyecto-europeo-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion/
ULIM	12/10/2021	Composites World	Industry	https://www.compositesworld.com/news/university-of-limerick-seeks-to-improve-composites-recycling-solutions
ULIM	02/11/2021	Silicon Republic	General	https://www.siliconrepublic.com/innovation/ul-composite-materials-vibes-project-horizon-2020-eu
ULIM	05/11/2021	The Clare Herald	General	https://clareherald.com/2021/11/ul-leads-way-on-composites-recycling-solution-73452/
ULIM	16/12/2021	Innovation in Textiles	Industry	https://www.innovationintextiles.com/composites/towards-

Partner	Date	Name of magazine/newspaper	Type	Link
				recyclable-composite-materials/
AITIIP	08/2022	RETEMA	Environmental sector	Revista digital Julio/Agosto 2022 - Especial Residuos RETEMA
AITIIP	10/2022	AVEP	Industry	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BgraPLAXop10rLPhbpi4ACYxnZ20lice/view
AITIIP	01/2023	Easy Engineering Magazine	Industry	https://easyengineering.eu/interview-with-aitiip-technology-centre/
BCIRC	03/2023	Interempresas	General	https://www.interempresas.net/Plastico/Articulos/470785-Entrevista-a-Oriol-Grau-CEO-de-BCircular.html

3.7 Participation in Events/ Fairs/ Info-days

Participating in relevant events and fairs are unique opportunities to reach further audiences with a wide range of backgrounds. Throughout the duration of the VIBES project, partners have planned to participate in at least 6 external events and fairs with a view to:

- present VIBES concept,
- keep in touch with the latest advances,
- share knowledge,
- establish contacts and interactions with stakeholders,
- promote VIBES actions and results,
- raise awareness.

To ensure consistency in the presentation and communication of the project, partners have at their disposal a common leaflet, a template for presentation slides, an infographic that can be produced as a poster or roll up, and a template for publications, all of which incorporate the VIBES logo and colours.

The consortium partners have been very active in their participation in relevant events and fairs, presenting VIBES among other projects and activities. The total target of participation in external events and fairs has been reached and surpassed. The following table lists the external events and fairs, in which partners have participated, presenting VIBES.

Table 7. Presentation of VIBES to relevant events

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
AITIIP	25/09/2020	Online pitch event / Presentation of circular economy projects to Isover-Saint Gobain.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/09/2020	Online pitch event / Presentation of circular economy projects to VEOLIA (Water, waste and energy management services).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	26/03/2021	Online pitch event / Presentation of circular economy projects to Grupo Antolín (car sector supplier).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	03/04/2001	Online pitch event / Presentation to DGA (Government of Autonomous Community of Aragón)	Policy Makers	Spain
AITIIP	16/04/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation of circular economy projects to Suez.	Industry	Spain
PLATA	08/05/2021	Presentation in Jaume I University about the participation of PLATA in European Projects, including VIBES, and PLATA's role in the innovation chain.	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	20/05/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation of circular economy projects to EDA (European Defence Agency).	Industry	Spain
PLATA	24/05/2021	Presentation in Space Port Master Plan Universidad de Cataluña about the participation of PLATA in European Projects, including VIBES, and PLATA's role in the innovation chain.	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	25/05/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation of	Industry	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		circular economy projects to Finsa (Wood transformation company).		
AITIIP	29/06/2021	Workshop on bridging the gap between academia and industry: training in European digitalization and circular economy projects/ Presentation of the project at Spanish Industry (CAAR).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/07/2021	Online pitch event / Presentation of VIBES objectives and expected results to Airbus.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/09/2021	Pitch event / Presentation of VIBES objectives and expected results to Siemens-Gamesa.	Industry	Spain
ARCHA	26-29/10/2021	Exhibitor in the ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES, and distributing 200 copies of VIBES leaflets.	Industry	Italy
PLATA	23/11/2021	Commercial presentation to the local event "Acto inauguración curso académico UNED".	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	29/11/2021	Presentation of VIBES objectives and expected results to industry, research centres and other institutions related to Horizon Europe at the workshop "Horizon Europe Clusters 6 and 5 opportunities in 2022".	Industry	Spain
AITIIP, ACCIONA	03-05/05/2022	Attendance of JEC World 2022 Fair, where the VIBES project was introduced to some of their	Industry	Paris

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		contacts and visitors to the fair.		
ARCHA	24-26/05/2022	Exhibitor in the Packaging Première & PCD Milan (Italy), where the experience gained during European Research & Innovation activities and projects, including VIBES, was described.	Industry	Italy
PLATA	15/07/2022	Presentation of VIBES in the aeronautical Course of University of Zaragoza	Students and workers	Spain
PLATA	24/09/2022	Presentation of VIBES in the Congress on Spatial rockets of the University of Zaragoza	Industry	Spain
BCIRC	18-20/10/2022	Presentation of VIBES at the Advanced Manufacturing Madrid 2022 Fair.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	15 - 17/02/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the Transfiere 2023 Exhibition.	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP & F&D	25/03/2023	Participation to the "JEC World 2023" event, where the VIBES project was introduced to the visitors of the fair.	Industry	Paris
AITIIP	30/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES research line at the "Foro Wake Up Spain!" event.	Technical	Spain
BCIRC	30/03/2023	Participation to the Strategic Immersion Day "Roadmap 2030 for a Sustainable Economy".	Industry	Barcelona, Spain
PLATA	12/05/2023	Participation to the TARMAC ARAGON FACILITIES meeting, presenting VIBES.	Industry	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
ARCHA	16-18/05/2023	Exhibitor in the “Packaging Première & PCD Milan” exhibition ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES.	Industry	Milan, Italy
AITIIP	17/05/2023	Participation to the “Meetech Spain” exhibition, where the VIBES project was introduced to the visitors to the exhibition.	Industry	Madrid, Spain
ARCHA	7-10/10/2023	Exhibitor in the ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES.	Industry	Rimini, Italy
JUNO COMPOSITES	01/11/2023	Presentation to End User discussing decarbonisation within the marine sector and presenting VIBES technology.	Industry	United Kingdom
AITIIP	15/12/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the workshop “The end of a product, the beginning of a material”.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	20/03/2024	Presentation of VIBES at the Transfiere 2024 Exhibition.	Industry	Málaga
ACCIONNA	5-7/04/2024	Disseminations of the VIBES at JEC World 2022 Fair.	Industry	Paris

3.8 Layman’s Report

The Layman’s report will be produced as a final report of the VIBES project, summarising the work of the project for a general audience. It will serve as a valuable marketing tool for promoting the environmental and economic benefits of the project results and extending the impact of the project beyond the area of implementation. It will clearly outline the achievements of the project and its long-term environmental and economic benefits to attract the interest of journalists and policymakers, along with those experts and stakeholders focusing on similar issues to those addressed by the project.

The Layman’s report will include the following information:

- The problem, introducing one or two paragraphs on the background to the project.
- Project overview, introducing the project's specific objectives, the benefits of the innovative solution (environmental, cost-benefit), the partners involved, as well as the project duration and budget.
- Results, introducing the innovative solutions in a non-technical way; this would be the core part of the report, describing the innovative solutions brought to the market thanks to the project.
- The market, introducing the target users and customers.
- The European added value, introducing the benefits at EU level.
- Contact information, including e-mail and website.

The Layman’s report will be between 5 and 10 pages in length, produced in electronic format. It will be presented in an attractive way, using eye-catching images where possible and presenting results in an easy-to-read way, such as tables, charts, and boxes.

3.9 Internal Communication

Daily communication between partners is achieved through email. Exchange of detailed information between Work Packages will be done also through email and by meetings.

To facilitate communication, the following emailing lists have been established.

Table 8. Internal mailing lists

LIST	MEMBERS
vibes_all@vibesproject.eu	It includes every participating member of VIBES consortium
vibes_technical@vibesproject.eu	It includes every member of VIBES consortium who is responsible for technical issues
vibes_administration@vibesproject.eu	It includes all members of VIBES consortium who are responsible for administrative issues
vibes_dissemination@vibesproject.eu	It includes all members of VIBES consortium who are responsible for the dissemination of the project

4. Dissemination Means and Channels

Dissemination activities aim at making the project results available to the scientific community, policy makers and industry, using scientific language and accurate statements.

4.1 Scientific Publications

It is an obligation and of interest to the consortium to widely disseminate the proposed new materials and technologies through qualified scientific publications. Scientific publications and conferences are important dissemination channels for sharing VIBES outcomes to academic and industrial target communities, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the results in their own work. It is expected that academic and research partners will take up the leading role in drafting scientific articles, assisted by all relevant consortium members. At least 6 scientific publications have been planned, including at least 4 articles in scientific journals and at least 2 posters in scientific conferences. The targets have been reached and surpassed.

In particular, VIBES partners participated in publishing the following peer-reviewed scientific articles, relevant to the VIBES approach and technological developments:

University of Limerick:

- Maurice N. Collins, Mario Culebras, Guang Ren, “Chapter 8 - The use of lignin as a precursor for carbon fiber-reinforced composites”, peer-reviewed chapter in the book with the title “Micro and Nanolignin in Aqueous Dispersions and Polymers: Interactions, Properties, and Applications”, published by Elsevier, 2022, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823702-1.00011-6>
- Rubio, M.C., Beaucamp, A., Stróżyk, M.A., Collins, M.N. (2022), “Lignin-based carbon fibers for high-performance Green Composites”, *Encyclopedia of Green Materials*, pp. 1–8, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-4921-9_155-1
- Beaucamp, A. et al. (2022) ‘Lignin for Energy Applications – State of the art, life cycle, technoeconomic analysis and future trends’, *Green Chemistry*, 2022, 24, pp. 8193–8226. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2GC02724K>
- Stróżyk, M.A. et al. (2024), ‘Decreasing the environmental impact of carbon fibre production via microwave carbonisation enabled by self-assembled nanostructured coatings’, *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials*, 7(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-024-00853-2>

AITIIP and the University of Limerick:

- Vidal, J. et al. (2023) ‘Use of covalent dynamic networks as binders on epoxy-based carbon fiber composites: Effect on properties, processing, and recyclability’, *Polymer Composites*, 44(11), pp. 7444–7456, Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.27636>

AITIIP

- Vidal, J. et al. (2024) ‘Strategies towards fully recyclable commercial epoxy resins: Diels–alder structures in sustainable composites’, *Polymers*, 16(8), p. 1024, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16081024>

SPECIFIC POLYMERS

- Guggari, S. et al. (2023) 'Vanillin-based epoxy vitrimers: Looking at the cystamine hardener from a different perspective', ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering, 11(15), pp. 6021–6031, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c00379>.
- Malburet, S. et al. (2023) 'Biobased Epoxy reactive diluents prepared from monophenol derivatives: Effect on viscosity and glass transition temperature of epoxy resins', RSC Advances, 13(22), pp. 15099–15106, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3RA01039B>
- Guggari, S. et al. (2024) 'Vanillin-based dual dynamic epoxy building block: A promising accelerator for disulfide vitrimers', Polymer Chemistry, 15(13), pp. 1347–1357, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4PY00038B>

4.2 Participation in Scientific Conferences

Participating in scientific conferences is a unique opportunity to reach audiences with various scientific and industrial backgrounds that are relevant to VIBES. Throughout the duration of the VIBES project, partners have planned to participate in at least 3 scientific conferences, in which VIBES approach, methodologies and results will be presented to relevant international scientific forums.

The consortium partners have already participated in 33 scientific conferences and forums, presenting VIBES approach and methodologies. The total target of participation in scientific conferences has been reached and surpassed. The following table lists the scientific conferences and related events, in which partners have participated, presenting VIBES.

Table 9. Presentation of VIBES approach to scientific conferences & events

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
ULIM	22/07/2021	Online presentation: "An abundant resource of biocarbon for advanced engineering applications" of the project at the International Conference on Resource Sustainability (icRS 2021)	Scientific community	International
DITF	15/09/2021	Presentation to Dornbirn GFC digital conference on "Low-cost carbon fibres: High-molecular weight Lignin combined with Low-Pressure Stabilization Technology".	Industry	International
ULIM	15/09/2021	Presentation to a network seminar (virtual), organised by	Industry	UK

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		the University of Bristol/ Catapult UK, on “Sustainable Composite materials for Wind Turbine Blades; Development of Lignin Fibres for Energy”		
BCIRC	14/10/2021	“Innovative and sustainable solutions for the nautic sector” presentation at the “INTERNATIONAL NAUTICTECH FORUM” conference.	Industry	Spain
DITF	09/11/2021	Presentation to the “Aachen-Dresden-Denkendorf International Textile - ADDITC” on “Stabilisation of polyacrylonitrile precursors by low-pressure technology for low-cost carbon fibres” presentation.	Industry	International
ULIM	21/10/2021	Online presentation on “Lignin - An abundant bioresource for next generation sustainable advanced engineering composites, at the Institute of Materials Mining and Minerals (IOM3) International Conference on Manufacturing (ICMAC).	Scientific community	International
PLATA	29/11/2021	Presentation at “Instituto Ingeniería de España” conference.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	02/02/2022	Reference to the VIBES innovation in the presentation of Mandala project at the “The European Biopolymer Summit 2022”.	Scientific community	UK
AITIIP	02/03/2021	Participation to “Webinar IA2”	Scientific	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		with the presentation “Cómo innovar en nuevos modelos de economía circular y envases/materiales más sostenibles”.	community	
AITIIP	17/02/2022	Participation to the scientific seminar of the International University Menéndez Pelayo and Polymers Institute with the presentation titled "Solid state polymers"	Scientific community	Spain
PLATA	03/03/2022	Presentation at "Desarrollo e innovación en Aeropuerto Internacional de Teruel" conference.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	23/03/2022	Online participation to the “S3 - 4th European Eco-plasturgy Congress” with a presentation on Thermosets towards a circular economy: sustainable recycling technologies.	Scientific community	Europe
AITIIP	06/04/2022	Poster’s exhibition on the 11th R&D European Framework Conference aiming to analyse the first year of the Horizon Europe Programme and the Spanish participation.	Industry	Spain
BCIRC	13/10/2022	Participation to the “Sustainability in Composites challenges and opportunities”	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	26/10/2022	Presentation of VIBES to technical audience in the 2022 edition of EMPACK within the Mandala’s project Final Conference.	Industry	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
AITIIP	14 - 16/11/2022	Presentation of VIBES to the European Summit of Industrial Biotechnology 2022 (ESIB 2022).	Industry	Austria
ULIM	8/03/2023	Participation to the SAMPE conference with “ Production of Lignin-based Carbon Fibers” presentation.	Scientific Community	Belfast, Northern Ireland
AITIIP	21-23/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the industrial audience of the eMobility Expo & World Congress.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	27-31/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the Wake Up Spain Forum.	Industry, Scientific community, policymakers	Spain
AITIIP	28/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the industrial audience of the Excellence Forum Automotive Cluster.	Industry	Online
SP	23-27/04/2023	Participation of VIBES to the APME : 14th Advanced Polymers via Macromolecular Engineering.	Scientific Community	France
AITIIP	04/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the “ECP4 sustainable composites” conference.	Technical	San Sebastián
SP	14-18/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the EUPOC	Scientific Community	Italy
PLATA	15/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya conference.	Scientific Community	Spain
F&D	20/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the 4th International Conference over	Scientific	Belgium, Gent

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		bio based and bio degradable textiles and polymers.	community	
PLATA	14-15/07/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the Antonio Gargallo University Foundation's conference for advances and development of the aeronautical and aerospace sector.	Scientific Community	Spain
LEITAT	13/09/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the Global Fiber Congress.	Scientific Community	Dornbirn, Austria
AITIIP	21/09/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the "Ippt-twin 1 International" conference.	Technical	Slovenia
AITIIP	23/10/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the "Polymer Connect" conference.	Technical	Valencia, Spain
AITIIP	31/10/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the Packnet conference: "Circular innovation in packaging: the road to a sustainable future."	Technical	Madrid, Spain
AITIIP	23/11/2023	Participation to the Quality Innovation Awards 2023 winning the "Innovation in Circular Economy and Zero Carbon Footprint" prize and presenting the VIBES lines of research.	Scientific community	Madrid, Spain
AITIIP	13/02/2024	Participation to the eMobility Expo World Congress with the VIBES presentation "New materials for the new vehicles".	Industry	Zaragoza
ULIM	30/04/2024	Presentation of VIBES project "Future opportunities for Lignin derived Advanced Materials" at the NOMATEN centre of	Scientific community	Poland

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		excellence in multifunctional materials for industrial and medical applications.		

4.3 Organisation of Events

In the frame of VIBES, several events have been and will be organised to serve the project’s objectives and promote the project and its outcomes. In more detail, the following types of events are scheduled as part of the project’s dissemination plan.

4.3.1 COMPOSIFORUM International Events

COMPOSIFORUM is the “Composites Forum for the Industry and Researchers”, organised by AITIIP in collaboration with the University of Zaragoza, as part of the AITIIP Chair (AITIIP CATEDRA) that advises and defines the strategic lines of Research, Development and Innovation projects of mutual interest between the University of Zaragoza and AITIIP foundation.

COMPOSIFORUM gathers experts in plastic composites and takes place every two years. The 2022 edition took place in Zaragoza on 17th November 2022 and focused on sustainability and circularity as strategic axes of the new economy. Prestigious speakers from the science and industrial arena participated. A lecture slot was reserved specifically for the dissemination of the VIBES project in 2022.

Due to an internal decision at the organisational level of AITIIP, it has been determined that the 2024 edition of COMPOSIFORUM will not take place. However, as mentioned in section 4.3.2., AITIIP exploited other opportunities for organising workshops to disseminate VIBES approach and results, which were not initially planned.

4.3.2 Demonstration and other Workshops

The organisation of three (3) demonstration workshops has been planned, addressed to industry and other VIBES stakeholders, in order to get the necessary feedback and engagement in the technology and the soundness of the VIBES concept. The following two (2) workshops were organised:

Figure 16. Demonstration workshop in PLATA

- One 5-hour workshop was organised together with HELACS project and focused on dismantling, collecting, sorting and directing processes and composites waste manipulation. This workshop took place on 29th July, 2021 at PLATA premises in Teruel (Spain) with the participation of Airbus, PLATA and AITIIP. There were 12 participants (33% female) from the aeronautic sector, technology providers, dismantling and recycling companies. During the workshop different aspects of VIBES and HELACS, advanced materials, efficient manufacturing, circular

economy and digitalisation were treated with the aim of gathering feedback and engagement. The event allowed us to confirm that the objectives of VIBES are aligned to industry and stakeholders. They are interested in the results and think that they will be useful in their future processes. They also expressed their intention to participate actively in project's activities and in future initiatives.

Figure 17. Demonstration workshop in CIRCE

PolynSPIRE project. There were 6 participants (20% female) from research and innovation centres. The workshop included a technical discussion about polyamide degradation processes and a visit to the lab in which the microwave solvolysis processes take place, which served as feedback for the green solvolysis process developed in VIBES. The event allowed us to confirm the alignment of the VIBES objectives to current research lines and the interest of the scientific community in its results.

- One 2-hour workshop was organised together with BIZENTE, polynSPIRE and LIFE RECYSITE projects on dealing with properties, industrial applications and end-of-life alternatives of thermoset composites. This workshop took place on 2nd July, 2021 at CIRCE premises in Zaragoza (Spain) with the aim of establishing synergies and interactions with

The third workshop will be organised during the fourth year of the project:

- One workshop will be dedicated to Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) and material certification -ISCC as well as the policies required to regulate the use of VIBES products and technology to reach the market and the society. This workshop will be combined with the second roundtable mentioned in section 4.1.3, involving members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

In addition to the above planned demonstration workshops, four more workshops were organised, as part of other relevant activities, in which VIBES was presented:

- A workshop organised by AITIIP on 22/3/2022, in Zaragoza (Spain), in which VIBES was presented as part of a training course related to moulding and plastic injection and circular economy, addressed to industry.
- A workshop organised by AITIIP, with the participation of speakers from AITIIP and LEITAT, on 18/5/2022, in Capri (Italy) at the SUM Symposium, with the title "[Sustainability of thermoset materials](#)", addressed to the scientific community and exposing the different approaches that are being followed for the treatment of thermosets, including the VIBES approach.
- On 02/12/2022, the University of Limerick hosted a workshop for secondary school students, highlighting the research conducted on lignin as part of the VIBES project.
- On 23/11/2023, AITIIP organised a workshop titled "Course on recycling and waste treatment" presenting the VIBES project.

4.3.3 Roundtables

In addition to the workshops mentioned above, two roundtables have been planned by Q-PLAN as part of the VIBES Stakeholders Board activities. The roundtables are organised at key turning points of the VIBES

project, hosting the VIBES Stakeholders Board with the participation of project partners, in order to open debate, share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy. The social changes and impact that VIBES may have in the society will be also explored.

The first roundtable event was held on November 29th, 2023 in a hybrid format at Disini Hotel, Montpellier, and online via MS Teams, bringing together crucial stakeholders and members of the VIBES Stakeholders' Board. Q-PLAN organised the event in detail, ensuring meticulous planning from tailored invitations to the distribution of pre-event materials. A total of 20 attendees, including 6 Stakeholders' Board members, actively participated in the discussions.

The overarching goal of the roundtable was to gather insights from external stakeholders, fostering a productive dialogue aimed at maximising the impact of project actions. Moderated by Dr. Eirini Efthymiadou, the event delved into key aspects of the project, particularly focusing on the design approaches of thermoset composites with intrinsic recyclability and their scale-up steps. These approaches encompassed biobased components, such as biobased bonding materials (BBMs), resins, and fibres. Expert presentations by leaders of Work Packages 1, 2 and 3 highlighted crucial milestones.

The interactive discussions explored the properties of innovative biobased materials, developed by the project, in relation to market needs and challenges for scaling up. Noteworthy topics included cost and supply chain dynamics, scalability issues, and the intricate nature of biobased materials.

Following the first roundtable, the second one is scheduled for November 2024.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) collects feedback from the activities of the VIBES Stakeholders Board and will present them in a final deliverable D6.6 "Feedback on key points from stakeholders' panel activities" on month 36.

4.3.4 Final Conference

By the end of the project, the VIBES final conference will take place. All project partners will participate in the organisation of this event under the lead of one of the partners, to be decided when considering the highest impact to be achieved. The aim of the conference will be to spread the accumulated knowledge and exploitation strategies and present the final achievements to scientists, industry, policy makers and generally to all interested parties, with a view to fostering industrial and research utilisation of the project results, as well as contribution to standards. Major stakeholders will be invited to participate in this event, including also all the students taking part in the VIBES training programme, described in Chapter 5. Keynote speakers will be invited to attract more public audience and the industrial and scientific community.

The VIBES partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks. All activities implemented towards the organisation of this conference will be reported in the fourth and final version of deliverable D6.5 "Report on communication, dissemination and training activities – Update 3".

5. Training Programme

A training programme was aligned with the communication and dissemination strategy with the aim of providing knowledge and skills to potential industrial collaborators and stakeholders of the VIBES project and to science and engineering students. The Training programme in the project represents the strategic vision of the Consortium in view of sharing and therefore implementing the open knowledge that has been gathered and generated within the project, both by the science students and by professionals in varied industrial sectors.

The training activities also contribute to the dissemination and therefore exploitation of the project results, contributing to raising awareness and providing novel competencies in the current and next generation of professionals.

The Project Coordinator (AITIIP) was responsible for designing, planning and organising the training programme, producing the deliverable D7.6 “Detailed content of VIBES skills for training: students & professionals”.

5.1 Training strategy

Training activities contribute to professional development, through advanced training of researchers and other key staff, science students, industry staff, and in general potential users of the knowledge generated by the project.

The complementary expertise of the partners within the project have a positive effect in generating cross-collaboration, a better capacity for training of young researchers and eventually fruitful staff exchange (e.g. between academia and enterprises).

The specific targets of the training activities are:

- **transfer** of knowledge within the participants including students, researchers and industrial staff.
- **spreading** of knowledge from both the academic and industrial professional within the project to researchers and students and to industrial staff outside the consortium, promoting S&T cohesion within the European research goals and so increase skills across Europe
- raising **awareness** of key stakeholders who are essential to successful exploitation and commercialization of the novel technology and products developed.

The approach used in the project is based on Open Science, focused on open dissemination and open materials.

It is generally accepted that Open Science leads to increased impact associated with wider sharing and re-use and could increase trust in science and in the reliability of scientific results.

In 2014, a core set of principles were drafted in order to optimise the reusability of research data, named the FAIR Data Principles. They represent a community-developed set of guidelines and best practices to ensure that data or any digital object are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable. This concept was used in VIBES in training design:

- **Findable:** The first thing to be in place to make data reusable is the possibility to find them. In VIBES cases, the training is available through an e-learning platform (aitemy learning)
- **Accessible:** The data can be retrievable by their identifier using a standardised and open protocol that guarantee a simple access. In this sense, the e-learning platform used, is intuitive and user-friendly.
- **Interoperable:** The data can be combined with and used with other data or tools.
- **Re-usable:** Ultimately, FAIR aims at optimizing the reuse of data. In this sense, VIBES created OERs (Open Education Resources) that could be used by other teachers and learners.

5.2 Objectives, Target Audiences and Themes

The training programme was designed and implemented with the aim of providing knowledge and skills on the topic of new recycling technologies for composite materials and the circular economy as well as to present and transfer the knowledge and results acquired during the project.

The training programme was promoted among the VIBES stakeholders that are included in the VIBES stakeholders’ database as well as Universities and Education Centres and other relevant contacts of the consortium partners. The stakeholders’ database was created by sharing relevant contacts and information among project partners using the “Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders” form (see Annex 1).

In particular, the training programme focused on the following types of stakeholders:

- Researchers from academia and technicians related to VIBES interconnected sectors (materials science, chemistry, chemical engineering, biotechnology, recycling and waste management)
- Industrial professionals who may potentially collaborate with and/ or be involved in the business that VIBES key exploitable results will generate (industrial developers, converters, dismantlers, waste managers and end-users).
- Science and engineering students (fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry), with the aim of creating a breeding ground of new talent for the creation of future jobs aligned with the new social and industrial needs.
- Anyone in the open society who is interested in the subject of green technologies and circular economy.

VIBES training is focused on some specific themes:

- Design and development of biobased materials
- Practical applications in industry
- Green technologies to recycle/reuse components.

VIBES validates a better use of resources demonstrating the high potential of the Circular Economy to implement a resilient energy union with forward-looking climate change policies. This validation is based on a technology evolution through scientific excellence (a first cost-effective recycling technology based on the development of smart BBM for the first time applied to composite thermoset plastic) which will equip to Chemical Industry to make Europe a stronger global actor and will this knowledge to design and implement the training activities.

5.3 Training Methodology

The training activities were held in a variety of formats and methods, both in presence - workshops, technological breakfast and face to face courses - and remotely - online training. Certificates of attendance are envisaged for all the training sessions, both online and in presence after completing a test.

5.3.1 Face to face training sessions

Venues for the training events were selected carefully and minimum requirements were the availability of hardware (projectors/wide screens) and internet connection that allowed for interactive activities to engage the audience and of course to guarantee the necessary security of the audience (COVID pandemic is an example).

The training events have been organised in Spain and Ireland; to increase the engagement, local language is highly recommended for the national events.

Events occurring in presence allow for higher involvement of the audience and longer sessions of training that may deepen the participants' knowledge on specific topics addressed by the event.

5.3.2 Online training sessions

The advantage of online training is the wider coverage and the possibility to re-play and learn following a personal path and rhythm. Remote sessions however are usually less interactive and do not allow for a profound discussion of the thematic covered by the event.

In this case, the online training will be an e-learning course and a recording of the summer course. It is available to the public on **aitemy learning platform** (<https://aitemy-learning.com/gb/>) and though a link on VIBES website.

The online learning content allow trainees to undertake the course at their own convenience. Course material is offered via recorded video and presentation slides. Upon completion of the course, AITIIP can release certificates to those who passed the requirements.

A link was integrated with the VIBES website, allowing it to further become the single point of reference for VIBES trainees.

5.3.3 Evaluation

The course includes formative assessment. There are different types of exercises and can be automatically checked. There is also a questionnaire in the face-to face event to value the trainees satisfaction.

5.4 Training activities

The training is being articulated around the following channels.

1. Research workshops for researchers and technicians.
2. Summer course for students, replicated at the University of Limerick summer school.
3. Free access to training material, generated by the summer course, through AITIIP e-learning platform (aitemy), open for both students and society.
4. Technological breakfast and workshops at AITIIP facilities for industrial professionals.

In each course or workshop special care will be taken so that there is a gender equality among participants, a balance between male and female participants.

5.4.1 Research Workshops for researchers and technicians

Three research-oriented workshops will be organised for researchers and technicians and will gather researchers from academia and industry related to VIBES interconnected sectors.

These workshops focus on researchers and technicians’ profiles mainly coming from Aragón and Spain. The three workshops will be organised following key milestones of the project, with the aim of transferring knowledge and gather feedback from peers.

A first workshop was held in February 2024 in PLATA facilities.

Tentatively, the rest of workshops will be organized in month 40 and at the end of the project.

It is expected that the partners responsible for the VIBES results take part as content developers and/or presenters.

5.4.2 Summer Training Course

The training for students is oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It will include a summer course, covering 30 hours of training. The course curriculum includes latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project. The VIBES consortium partners prepare the content of the training. The training was launched in May 2023. Twenty-four (24) hours were developed as an e-learning course, with a final face to face Summer Course in PLATA.

The contents of the course were:

- Design and development of biobased materials
- Practical applications in industry
- Green technologies to recycle/reuse components.

The following contents has been developed:

Module 1: Design and development of strategies to include thermoset plastics into circular economy (10 hours)

Explanation: development of CANs and biobased resins

- CANs general approach what are these materials → 1.5 Hour
- Supramolecular approach → 2 Hours
- Vitrimers approach → 2 Hours

- D-A approach → 2 hours
- Synthesis of bio resins → 1.5 Hour
- Use of green solvents → 1 Hour

Module 2: Biobased and improved fibres a key for the success of a composite (8 hours)

Explanation: manufacture and modify the structure and chemical properties of the textile reinforcements used in composite materials

- Linseed material: Possible configurations and potential → 1.5 Hour
- Carbon fibre and chemical modification of its surface to boost its properties and allow recyclability → 2.5 Hours
- Fabrication of biobased CF & Sizings development → 2.5 Hours
- Scaling up and fabrication of biobased CF → 1.5 Hour

Module 3: Application of VIBES materials and technologies in the industry (6 hours)

Explanation: Within this module different sectors explain the interest, potential and applications that the developments of the project will have in their market

- Applications in the construction sector → 1.5 Hour
- Applications in the aeronautic sector → 1.5 Hour
- Applications in the naval industry → 1.5 Hour
- Potential of solvolysis in the industry of composites (B-circ) → 1.5 Hour

Module 4: Face-to-face summer course (6 hours)

- Composites, recycling techniques and their market impact.
- Use of enzymes as a method of recycling composites.
- Covalent networks in thermoset composite.
- Cutting of composite parts for better dismantling and recycling.
- Redesign of materials to include in a circular economy - Reinforcement and matrix.
- Visit to the facilities.

Under the coordination of AITIIP, the partners collaborated in the creation of the contents from 18th month of the project. The practical session was done in PLATA facilities on 15th September 2023 during around 6 hours. 16 persons participated directly and one through online connection. An evaluation was done at the end of the course.

The summer course was organised in Teruel Campus, a rural area in south Aragon region that belongs to the University of Zaragoza and located next to PLATA facilities which was visited in order to familiarise future employees with the industry environment of vision, problem identification and solution implementation from the circular economy perspective.

The summer course, organised jointly with "Antonio Gargallo" University Foundation, aims to promote cooperation between the University of Zaragoza, the Public Administrations of the Autonomous Community of Aragon and the institutions and socio-economic agents of the province of Teruel for the development of the University Campus of Teruel, by carrying out actions and setting up its own projects or those agreed with companies or public and private institutions.

The Summer University of Teruel (UVT) is a programme of activities of the "Antonio Gargallo" University Foundation, consisting of a range of courses, seminars, workshops and scientific meetings held throughout the year, although preferably during the summer period.

The UVT is a substantial part of the summer activity of the University of Zaragoza, being this link compatible with a clear vocation of universality that also allows programming activities in collaboration with other universities or with other non-university bodies of recognised prestige, from the social and academic point of view; this is the case of certain training activities linked to public or private institutions. The offer is intended to be broad and plural, both in terms of topics and methodological approaches.

UVT advertised the course on its website: [Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials Through a Greener Recycling Technology | Fundación Universitaria Antonio Gargallo \(unizar.es\)](https://unizar.es)

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials Through a Greener Recycling Technology

Ciencia y Tecnología Teruel

Fecha evento:
15/05/2023 to 15/09/2023

Director/Directores:
Dña. Eva Sanchis. Responsable de Formación. Socióloga con Máster en Técnicas Educativas Emergentes, en Gamificación y Narrativa Transmedia, en Comunidades Europeas y Unión Europea y en Investigación de Mercados.

Horas lectivas totales: 30

Precio de la matrícula:
Matrícula general: 20 euros.

[Matrícula](#)

Objetivos:

El alumno tendrá capacidad para gestionar la información procedente de diversas fuentes, valorando su relevancia, fiabilidad y pertinencia para un propósito determinado, analizándola y organizándola. Además facilitará al alumno el reconocimiento de los conceptos básicos sobre reciclabilidad de composites y su aplicación práctica a distintos sectores como construcción, aeronáutica o naval y su sensibilización en la importancia y repercusión de las tecnologías de reciclado de productos plásticos en particular y de la economía circular y sostenibilidad en general.

Objectives:

The student will have the ability to manage information from various sources, assessing its relevance, reliability, and relevance for a specific purpose, analyzing it and organizing it.

In addition, it will facilitate the student's recognition of the basic concepts on the recyclability of composites and their practical application to different sectors such as construction, aeronautics or naval and their awareness of the importance and impact of recycling technologies for plastic products in particular and for the circular economy and sustainability in general.

Programa:

The above Summer Course was replicated in the summer programme of the University of Limerick in May 2024.

Leading experts on composite materials gathered at the University of Limerick to discuss the future of composite materials and their key role in the transition to a biobased economic model. Lively discussion

took place with distinguished members of the audience (online and in person) from both industry and academia.

The participation included 30 people in person and 25 online. Two LinkedIn posts about this training activity generated well over 5k impressions.

The agenda was the following:

- A quick fatigue assessment method for fibre reinforced composites. Dr Akshay Hejjaji (UL)
- Carbon Fibre production and life cycle assessment. Dr Anne Beaucamp (UL)
- New Resins, BBMs and Recycling. Dr Julio Vidal (AITIIP)
- Modelling and composite design Dr Giovanni Zucco (UL, School Of Engineering)
- Future CFRP products and commercial directions (Dr Saul Buchanan (JUNOComposites)
- Integrating Composites with Diverse Materials for Automotive and Aerospace Applications. Dr Kashif Bangash (UL)
- Latest techniques for composite manufacture. Dr Ronan O'Higgins (Head of School of Engineering, UL)
- Final comments Prof. Maurice N. Collins (UL)

The visit to PLATA facilities can be replicated by ACCIONA and IDEC in their own premises.

In both cases, the course was in English to facilitate its implementation in each facility and encourage the participation of other students from any EU member-state.

In parallel to the above training, ATIIP and University of Limerick will extend the research results generated by the project by launching at least 3 MSc theses and 2 PhD theses.

5.4.3 E-learning

As it is mentioned previously, to develop the Summer Course online content was created that complements the practical activities.

The e-learning includes a menu so that the trainees can choose if they prefer a linear learning or their own path.

MENU

- Introduction
- Introduction
- Overview
- What about CANs? ✓
- What about CANs?
- What about CANs?
- What about CANs?
- This is an exercise ✓
- Conclusion
- Great!

01 Overview

What about CANs ?

Dissociative mechanism

Diels-Alder

Loss of crosslink integrity

⇒ Abrupt decrease of viscosity

⇒ Loss of network connectivity

This project has received funding from the programme under grant agreement No 101023190 the Bio-based Industries Consortium.
Diels-Alder adduct is one of the examples of dynamic bond with dissociative
2020 research and Innovation and Innovation programme and

VIBES

< PREV NEXT >

It also includes speech and subtitles.

MENU

- Introduction ✓
- Introduction
- Introduction
- Introduction
- Introduction
- Introduction
- Introduction
- Overview
- This is an exercise ✓
- Conclusion
- Great!

VIBES

This is an exercise

What are the different types of CANs?

Dissociative

Alternative

Cohesive

Associative

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

SUBMIT ✓

The interactive exercises allow the trainees to check their knowledge.

If their answer is wrong, the course informs the trainees, and they can decide if they continue or return to the exercise through the menu.

In order to ensure open access to the developed content and maximise the returns to society, the summer course was recorded. An open version for a wider student audience and the society in general has been uploaded and made free for use through AITIIP e-learning platform, aitemy: <https://aitemy-learning.com/gb/>, also shared in the [training section](#) of the project website.

The e-learning content was made available as soon as the summer courses in Teruel and Limerick took place.

The e-learning content is expected to reach at least 100 students and other stakeholders interested in the technological areas related to the VIBES project.

A certificate is handed to those having finalised the summer training course, described in section 5.4.2, and the open e-learning version of the VIBES training programme.

5.4.4 Training for Industrial Professionals

The training for industrial professionals will be organised by AITIIP.

At least 40 Spanish industrial professionals will take part in the event. International experts could be invited. The language of the event will be Spanish.

In addition, one workshop for industrial professionals will be organised at AITIIP facilities about eco-design using biobased materials. The duration will be half day. The language of the workshop will be Spanish, but the possibility to organise it in English will be evaluated if there is an interest from European industrial professionals to take part. The contents will be created by the VIBES consortium partners and will be taught by AITIIP in collaboration with other partners. In order to maximise its impact, this workshop will be organised together with other important event whenever possible.

Furthermore, professional visits to VIBES industrial partners (IDEC, ACCIONA and PLATA) have been also organised for potential stakeholders and open to industrial collaborators interested in the fields addressed by the VIBES project.

5.5 Training activities calendar

#	Date	Venue	Format	Description	Audience
1	M24	Online (aitemy platform)	Course	E-learning contents for design and development of biobased materials, practical applications in industry and green technologies to recycle/reuse components.	Academia, industry, open society
2	M27	Spain	Course	Summer school course. The practical training for students was oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It included the e-learning contents, until covering 30 hours of training.	Academia, industry, open society
3	M33	Spain	Workshop	First workshop for researchers and technicians organized in PLATA facilities.	Academia, industry
4	M36	Ireland	Course	Summer school course. The training for students is oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It will include a summer course, covering 30 hours of training. The course curriculum will include latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project.	Academia, industry, open society
5	M40	Spain	Workshop	Workshop for researchers and technicians will be organised at AITIIP. The duration will be half day. The language of the workshop will be Spanish.	Academia, industry
6	M44	Spain	Lecture/seminar	Organisation of one technological breakfast for industrial professionals in the fields addressed by the VIBES project. International experts could be invited. The language of the event will be Spanish.	Industry
7	M46	Spain	Workshop	Workshop for industrial professionals will be organised at AITIIP facilities about eco-design using	Industry

#	Date	Venue	Format	Description	Audience
				biobased materials. The duration will be half day. The language of the workshop will be Spanish.	
8	M48	Spain	Workshop	Workshop for researchers and technicians will be organised at AITIIP. The duration will be half day. The language of the workshop will be Spanish.	Workshop

VIBES		Last updated: 30/9/2021																																																											
		2021												2022												2023												2024												2025											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May							
		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48												
WP6: Communication, Dissemination and Training																																																													
T6.3- Dissemination activities																																																													
Scientific publications																																																													
Participation in scientific conferences																																																													
COMPOSIFORUM international events																																																													
Demonstration workshops																																																													
Roundtables																																																													
Final Conference																																																													
Feedback on key points from stakeholders' panel activities																																																													
T6.4- Training activities																																																													
Research workshops																																																													
Summer training course																																																													
E-learning																																																													
Training for industrial professionals																																																													
Detailed content of VIBES skills for training: students & professionals																																																													

7. Performance Indicators, Monitoring and Reporting

7.1 Performance Indicators and Monitoring

The implementation of communication and dissemination strategy is monitored on an on-going basis according to the level of realisation of the communication and dissemination objectives and outcomes that have been set up. The frequent evaluation of communication and dissemination activities allows to monitor and measure their impact and, if necessary, adapt them in order to increase the project’s visibility and awareness. The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager has the overall responsibility of the monitoring and evaluation of VIBES communication and dissemination activities, although the project partners are also expected to help by continuously monitoring and evaluating the publicity and communication activities they carry out.

Analytical measures and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are used in order to monitor the implementation and assess the impact of communication, dissemination and training activities. A number of metrics employed for the monitoring and evaluation of these activities are provided in the following Table, together with their target values. Besides the quantitative metrics indicated below, qualitative data will be also gathered by eliciting feedback from stakeholders, on all occasions that allow direct contact with them (e.g. events organised or attended).

Table 10. KPIs and target values

Achievement KPI ⁸	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
Number of Stakeholders Board Members	At least 10 (at least 30% female)	11 (55 % female)			
Number of pieces of news posted on VIBES website	N/A	43	Number of visits to the VIBES website	15,000 unique visitors by the end of the project (indicative)	3,400
Number of posts	N/A	138	Number of followers in	2,000 followers	250

⁸ The essential KPIs for monitoring the implementation of the communication, dissemination and training activities are marked in bold; they are those with target values that are specific and not indicative (specified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement). The rest of the KPIs are for assessing the impact of the communication, dissemination and training activities; they are considered as equally important, but their target values are indicative at this stage (unless they are specified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement) and may be later adapted based on the experience gathered.

Achievement KPI ⁸	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
on VIBES social media accounts		(Twitter) 138 (LinkedIn) 138 (Facebook)	the VIBES social media accounts	(indicative) (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube)	(Twitter) 615 (LinkedIn) 192 (Facebook) 11 (YouTube)
Number of project leaflets designed	2 (one in the beginning and one at the mid-end)	1	Number of distributed promotional materials	2,000 copies of leaflets distributed in project/external events (indicative)	935
Number of project infographics designed	1	1			
Number of project videos produced	2 (one in the beginning and one at the end)	1	Number of project video viewers	500 (indicative)	411
Number of e-newsletters	8 (2 per year, covering the activities developed every semester)	5	Number of subscribers to e-newsletters	500 (indicative)	267
Number of press releases (in English)	At least 6	6	Number of press release publications in local media	N/A	19

Achievement KPI ⁸	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
			Number of citizens reached via media publications (press releases)	N/A	12,715
Number of radio or TV programmes that VIBES was communicated to	2	3			
Number of articles published in industry magazines	At least 4	3	Number of industrial stakeholders reached via media publications (industry magazines)		
Number of events /fairs/ info-days in which partners participated presenting VIBES	At least 6	32	Number of stakeholders (industry) reached via VIBES participation in exhibitions and trade fairs	1,500	4,053
			Number of participants (industrial stakeholders & policy makers) in events in which partners presented VIBES	500	1,292
Number of scientific papers published	At least 6 (at least 4 articles in scientific journals and 2 posters in conferences)	9			
Number of scientific	At least 3	33	Number of participants (scientific community &	3,000	3,123

Achievement KPI ⁸	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
conferences in which partners participated presenting VIBES			industry) in scientific conferences in which partners presented VIBES		
Number of COMPOSIFORUM international events organised	At least 2	1	Number of participants in COMPOSIFORUM international events	100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	80
Number of demonstration workshops organised for industry and stakeholders	3	2	Number of participants in the demonstration workshops	50 participants in total (indicative) (at least 30% female – indicative)	18
Number of other workshops organised	N/A	4	Number of participants in other organised workshops (industry and scientific community)	N/A	139
Number of organised roundtables	2	1	Number of stakeholders that participated in roundtables	10 per roundtable	20
			Number of participants in the Final Conference	At least 100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of summer training courses,	2	1	Number of participants in the summer training courses	30 students per course (at least 30%	16+1 (module 4)

Achievement KPI ⁸	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
organised as part of the training programme				female - indicative)	
			Number of participants on e-learning platform: AITEMY		
Number of research-oriented workshops organised for technicians and professionals from academia and industry, as part of the training programme	3	1	Number of professionals (academia and industry) participated in training (research-oriented, technological breakfast, workshop)	At least 100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	45
Number of training activities for industrial professionals, organised as part of the training programme	2 (one technological breakfast and one workshop)	0		At least 100 (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	
Number of MSc theses launched	3	N/A			
Number of PhD theses launched	2	N/A			

The target of reaching 100,000 citizens refers to more than one communication KPIs, including number of citizens reached through website visits, social media, video views, e-newsletters, published articles/press releases, digital channels etc. In total, it has been estimated from available data that at least **20,694 citizens** have been reached through communication activities. However, there are not enough data available, as reported by project partners' activities, which can be used to correctly estimate the total figure of citizens reached.

In particular, a corrective step has been implemented regarding the estimation of number of citizens and industrial stakeholders reached via media publications and participation to exhibitions and trade fairs, as these numbers are not directly available and are only based on the information provided by the media publishers and the event organisers.

In addition, certain strategic steps regarding online communication have been adapted to meet the corresponding targets:

- The number of VIBES social media posts has increased by posting twice per week in each social media account of the project; this approach has significantly increased the VIBES social media followers, in particular the LinkedIn followers.
- The e-newsletter subscribers have been linked to LinkedIn followers by publishing e-newsletters through VIBES LinkedIn account; this approach has had an immediate impact in significantly increasing the number of people that the e-newsletters reached.
- The VIBES social media posts have provided direct links to specific sections of the VIBES website with interesting content, such as news, video, training material, publications etc., leading to a significant increase of the number of visitors to the project website; we will continue to monitor the website and social media KPIs and if needed we may consider paid campaigns in June 2024.
- The communication with sister projects and other initiatives has been intensified, leading to an increase of reposts of our news and social media posts in their online channels, and vice versa; this approach has provided interesting material for our online channels while it has also had an immediate multiplier effect in reaching a wider audience.

In any case, it has been made evident that even though the number of unique visits to the VIBES website has significantly increased by following the above strategic steps, the corresponding target value may not be reached by the end of the project. However, based on the available information, different communication and dissemination activities have proven to be more effective in reaching and even exceeding this target, such as publication of articles and press releases in local press and industry magazines and participation to events such as exhibitions and trade fairs.

7.2 Reporting

Communication and dissemination reporting is essential for keeping track of all the communication and dissemination activities that are carried out. Therefore, the project partners are expected to continuously report all their relevant activities on a six-months periodic report and to contribute to the continuous monitoring of VIBES communication and dissemination activities.

In order to facilitate the reporting of each communication and dissemination activity undertaken, four reporting tools have been designed and shared with all partners, as shown in the following Table.

Table 11. Reporting tools for monitoring the communication and dissemination activities

Annex	Reporting Tool	Coverage	When
11	Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template	All communication and dissemination activities, which partners were involved in during every 6 months period.	Every 6 months
12	News Reporting Template	News about project developments which partners are involved with.	Throughout the project
13	Event Reporting Form	Every single event organised or event in which partners participated.	Within 30 days following the completion of the event
14	External Conferences and Events Template	Any external conference/ event identified by partners, which is considered relevant to VIBES and beneficial to attend.	Throughout the project

7.2.1 Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template

During each project semester, all partners are expected to complete the “Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template” (Annex 10) reporting all communication and dissemination activities that they carried out during the previous six months.

It is an Excel file that should be sent at the end of each project semester to Q-PLAN. All the information required must be provided. The European Commission collects all these data from the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN). Therefore, for each activity each partner should indicate the following information:

- Partner name
- Date of activity (in order of occurrence / earlier first)
- Place of activity (online or physical location)
- Type of activity (select from drop-down list)
- Title of publication or event (if applicable)
- Title of article or presentation (if applicable)
- Type of audience (select from drop-down list)
- Size of audience (number of persons per type of audience)
- Language used / countries reached out
- Role and description of partner organisation’s involvement
- Type of project promotional material used (e.g. leaflets, infographic, project presentations)

- Quantity of project promotional material handed out (number of copies distributed per promotional material)
- Other partners or external organisations involved
- Short description of the activity
- Evidence: URL, screenshot, photo (given that the target group has given its consent)
- Significant contacts made (if relevant)
- Other comments (if relevant)

7.2.2 News Reporting Template

Partners are expected to share news about important project developments, including project approach, methodologies and results, organisation of events etc, by completing the “News Reporting Template” (Annex 11). The news reporting template includes the following information:

- News title
- News main content / description (a couple of paragraphs)
- Key words / hashtags (for social media)
- Relevant picture (if available)

The completed news reporting template should be sent to Q-PLAN, in order to communicate the corresponding news on the project website and social media.

7.2.3 Event Reporting Form

For each completed event (workshop, conference, etc.), partners are requested to complete the “Event Reporting Form” (Annex 12) providing information regarding the event that they were involved in. This form should be sent to Q-PLAN within 30 days after the end of the event and the event should also be communicated to Q-PLAN, in advance, for promotional purposes.

It is a structured document that includes the following information:

- Event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendees including % of female attendees, duration)
- Goals and relevance to the project
- Organisation of the event (if applicable)
- Dissemination activities within the event
- Structure of the event
- Outcomes of the event
- Evaluation of the event
- Annexes (list of participants, agenda, photos, presentations, if applicable)

7.2.4 External Conferences and Events Template

The “External Conferences and Events Template” is an excel file (Annex 13), that partners may complete each time they identify an event (e.g. conference, workshop, seminar etc.) relevant to VIBES and in which VIBES partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. Each partner should share this file with Q-PLAN, which will then be communicated to all project partners.

For each identified external conference or any other relevant event, each partner should indicate the following information:

- Event Name
- Thematic Focus
- Date and Location
- Registration Fees
- Specific requirements for participation
- Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)
- Link to event website
- Name of partner

8. Conclusions

The current document constitutes the second update version of the “Report on Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities” of the VIBES project. It has been developed by Q-PLAN, in collaboration with AITIP and input from all partners, under Work Package 6 “Communication, dissemination & training”.

With reference to the initial report elaborated in D6.2. and its first update elaborated in D6.3, this report describes the objectives and the defined framework of project’s communication, dissemination and training strategy and provides a second update of both the implemented and the foreseen communication, dissemination and training activities and corresponding channels, following the experience of the 36 months of the project’s implementation.

The project consortium has so far managed to create a consistent and recognisable visual identity and branding for the VIBES project and has made considerable efforts to reach out to the targeted stakeholder groups and relevant networks. Our communication, dissemination and training activities are focused on raising awareness about the project’s approach and development, through the project online media, activities, synergies, contribution with new knowledge and through participation in relevant events.

Our future efforts will focus on deepening the connections made and networks built in local and EU context, to maximize the visibility and outreach of VIBES. To this end, all partners should keep on actively contributing to the communication and dissemination activities through the exploitation of the defined dissemination tools and channels, promoting and multiplying publicity of the project’s aims and achievements and disseminating targeted messages to all relevant stakeholders.

By communicating and disseminating the project’s tangible and intangible assets through the most effective channels and tools to timely reach the targeted groups, VIBES will be able to not only go beyond its ambitious Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) but most importantly to lay the foundations for the successful rollout, replication and thus sustainability of its outcomes.

Annex 1. Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders

VIBES		Contact list of VIBES stakeholders												
Group list	Sub-group list	No	Group (please select from drop down list)	Sub-group (please select from drop down list)	Contact name	Gender (M/F)	Contact email	Organisation (if applicable)	Website (if applicable)	Country	Nominated by VIBES consortium partner	Stakeholders Board Member (YES/NO/MAYBE)	Comments	FOLLOW UP
Industrial developers	Thermoset composite material developers													
Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users	Composite recyclers													
Technology/ Innovation Experts	Aeronautical													
Impact multipliers	Naval													
Other (please specify in comments)	Construction													
	Energy													
	Waste management													
	Logistics													
	Transport													
	Academics and/or Researchers													
	Technology and/or Innovation consultants													
	Policy makers													
Media/ journalists or bloggers														
	Other (please specify in comments)													

Annex 2. Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent Form

Declaration of Acceptance

(for individuals appointed as members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board in their individual capacity)

I, the undersigned, _____ certify that I have read and agree to abide by the VIBES Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference.

I pledge that I will participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board in my individual capacity and as such I may not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the VIBES consortium.

I certify that no conflict of interests exists that could be considered as prejudicial to my independence in acting as a member of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the Stakeholders Board, unless the VIBES consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.

I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as member of the Stakeholders Board as described in the Terms of Reference.

I consent that any input or contribution I provide as member of the VIBES Stakeholders Board may be used by the VIBES consortium for reporting purposes or to align the products and technologies offered by VIBES with the needs of final users to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.

Name of participant

Date

Signature

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are

We are contacting you in the framework of VIBES, a project funded by the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

VIBES aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

A detailed description of the project and description of how VIBES handles personal data is available through the project’s web site www.vibesproject.eu.

Project:

VIBES – Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology, based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials.

Project Coordinator:

Organisation name: FUNDACION AITIIP

Address: Polígono Industrial Empresarium, Calle Romero Nº12, 50720 Zaragoza, Spain

Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager:

Organisation name: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS P.C.

Address: 11 El. Venizelou str, 55133 Kalamaria, Thessaloniki, Greece.

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	Project Coordinator	Pere Castell	pere.castell@aitiip.com
2	Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager	Eirini Efthymiadou	info@vibesproject.eu ; efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr

What we need from you

We need you to participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board with a view to participate in project activities, including demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, and provide your views and feedback to guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.

To effectively carry out the activities of the Stakeholders Board, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number).

- Some basic demographics (gender, nationality).
- Your professional information (organisation, job position, field of expertise).
- Your education information.
- Your opinions on the subject matter(s) of relevant events.

Why we need your data & what we will do with them

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out activities related to the Stakeholders Board and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of your participation in such activities. We also need to record your data to keep track of the implementation of the activities. The project’s deliverables that will be derived by activities in which you participate will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you.

We will share your data with other project partners that are also involved in this task and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project’s evaluation.
- EU agencies and other authorities for project’s auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project activities and also to inform you about the project’s progress (e.g. by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How you can withdraw your consent

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in the Stakeholders Board and its related activities, including demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, to provide my views and feedback to guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in future activities of VIBES.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding VIBES activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Annex 3. Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference

Introduction

You have been invited to take part in the **VIBES Stakeholders Board (SB)** because you were nominated by at least one of the VIBES consortium partners as a key stakeholder. The following Terms of Reference are aimed at helping you understand what this involves before you decide to participate. Please take the time to read this document carefully and ask for any clarifications you may require.

VIBES in a nutshell

VIBES is a 4-year Research and Innovation Action running from June 2021 to May 2025, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

The VIBES project aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative and cost-efficient **green technology solution** to resolve the **end-of-life issues of thermoset composites**, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. To reach its purpose, VIBES will initially focus on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised **100% Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)**. In addition, the project will design and develop biobased thermoset composites, with the intention to **place industrial biobased and recyclable substituent composite materials in the market**. The developed materials will be validated for optimum performance/ cost ratio in 3 **high-demand industrial sectors**: aeronautical, construction and naval industries. Finally, a **greener, fast, economic, and non-toxic recycling technology** to treat the smart VIBES composites will be developed and implemented at pilot level. As a result, the decomposed materials will be **recovered and valorised as new feedstocks** for the development of new products. The whole system will be defined, from the dismantling of the parts of the composite, to collecting and directing to the recycling plant, receiving, handling and sorting of the materials.

In this context, the Stakeholders Board (SB) of VIBES will consist of experts and representatives of various stakeholder groups in the whole value chain of VIBES, with activity in both local and European settings, who will be strategically involved in key stages of the project to contribute with their expertise and represent the views and interests of their stakeholder groups, in order to better guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.

The VIBES project brings together a consortium of **13 partners across 7 different EU member states**. You can find more information about VIBES and the consortium by visiting www.vibesproject.eu.

Role and benefits

Role

The SB is set up and operate to share its knowledge and expertise with the consortium of the project in key implementation stages. The role of the SB in the context of the project may be summed up as follows:

- **Provide feedback and insights for the development process of VIBES innovations** such as the bio-based materials and the recycling technology, by participating in discussions and activities as prospective users of the developed materials and technology, to enhance their practical value and usability; as well as

- **Be actively involved in VIBES dissemination activities** to create a multiplier effect in spreading the word on the project’s value propositions, knowledge and impact as well as facilitating the market uptake of the project’s results.

To fulfil this role, it is foreseen that the SB, during the course of the project, will participate in VIBES demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, and will interact on ad-hoc basis if necessary:

- **Demonstration workshop:** it is expected that the SB will help articulate and lead the organisation of at least one demonstration workshop, addressed to industry and other VIBES stakeholders, in order to get the necessary feedback and engagement in the technology and the soundness of the VIBES concept.
- **Roundtables:** it is expected that the SB will participate in at least two roundtables, to be organised at key turning points of the VIBES project, in order to open debate, share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept and its implementation.
- **Technological breakfast:** it is expected that specific members of the SB will participate in at least one technological breakfast for industrial professionals, to be organised as part of the VIBES training programme, in order to share their views and experience in the fields addressed by the VIBES project.
- **Ad-hoc interactions:** if deemed necessary, the support of the SB (either in its entirety or of specific members based on their particular expertise) will be requested for ad hoc needs.

Benefits

The project provides **several benefits to its SB members**, such as:

- **Networking opportunities and visibility** as an expert stakeholder in a large multi-stakeholder community in the VIBES domain.
- **First access to meaningful insights, knowledge and results** generated exclusively within the context of the project and its activities.
- Unique opportunity to **align the VIBES bio-based materials and recycling technology with the needs of their stakeholders** to ensure that they make the most out of their value propositions.

Terms of membership and Management

Terms of membership

The SB shall be composed of eminent experts coming from diverse backgrounds to offer a blend of expertise that represents various groups of stakeholders from the VIBES whole value chain (such as industrial developers and users, academics and researchers, technology and innovation consultants, policy makers, media representatives etc.) and experts involved in projects and initiatives that are relevant to VIBES. These experts will provide VIBES with valuable feedback aimed at aligning the project’s outcomes with the needs of users and stakeholders. Along these lines, at least 10 members of the Stakeholders Board (SB) will be initially selected with the possibility to further expand the SB in the future in order to draw from additional expertise and increase the outreach of VIBES. New members could be appointed to the SB when necessary and as the project evolves.

Although members of the SB may be selected because of their affiliations with key organisations, they serve on the SB in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder

communities. **Members of the SB may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them** or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the VIBES consortium. Members of the SB are appointed for the entire duration of the project (48 months, from 1 June 2021 to 31 May 2025). If due to job changes or attrition, an SB member loses links to important networks or constituencies, the consortium may decide to fill in this gap by appointing additional members.

The contribution of SB members is on a **pro bono basis**, apart from the cases in which physical travel is involved and a specific budget for their reimbursement is foreseen in the framework of the project. In such cases, the travel and accommodation expenses of SB members will be reimbursed by the project. Moreover, participation in the SB is **entirely voluntary**. There will be no adverse consequences if an SB member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, SB members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (see next section). They may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

Management

The SB is managed by the **Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager** that facilitates the communications and interactions between the SB and the consortium, ensuring that SB members are not overloaded. The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager will also ensure that for each task requiring input from the SB, the partners have beforehand prepared an action plan and all necessary briefings and material. Only then, will the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager introduce a partner who may directly communicate with the SB in order to achieve the expected goals at each time.

Contact point

Any enquiry, complaint or concern about any aspect of your experience as a member of the Stakeholders Board (SB) can be addressed to the **VIBES Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager** that oversees the set up and manages the SB. The contact details of the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager are provided below:

VIBES Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS P.C.

Contact person: Eirini Efthymiadou

Phone: +30 2310 411 191

Email: info@vibesproject.eu; efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr

Project website: www.vibesproject.eu

Annex 4. Document and Presentation Templates

VIBES

Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Grant Agreement 101023190

DX.Y “Title of Deliverable”

Work Package X

Responsible Partner: Name of Partner

Bio-based Industries Consortium

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu

VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

VIBES has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

 VIBES Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

www.vibesproject.eu

IMPROVING RECYCLABILITY OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH A GREENER RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON REVERSIBLE BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

Title
Location
Date

Name
Email
Organisation

This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

 VIBES Green
Chemistry
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IMPROVING RECYCLABILITY OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH A GREENER RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON REVERSIBLE BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

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Annex 5. VIBES Presence on Social Media

VIBES Page and Metrics on Twitter

VIBES Project 2021- 2025
@VIBESEU2

VIBES: an #innovative and #cost-efficient #green technology solution for #thermoset composites' end-of-life.
@CBE_JU @EU_H2020 funded project.

vibesproject.eu Joined June 2021

787 Following 250 Followers

Posts Replies Highlights Articles Media Likes

VIBES Project 2021- 2025 @VIBESEU2 · May 10 Promote ...

★ Thank you all for joining our workshop "Composite Materials: State of Art and Future Prospects", organized by VIBES & @BioUptake and hosted by @UL. We explored future CFRP products, commercial directions & the integration of composites for automotive and aerospace applications.

28 day summary with change over previous period

Post impressions

1,445 ↑ 36.2%

Followers

250

VIBES Page and Metrics on LinkedIn

VIBES Project 2021-2025
A green technology solution for thermoset composites' end-of-life.
Biotechnology Research · 615 followers · 11-50 employees

Message Following

Home About **Posts** Jobs People Insights

All Images Videos Articles Documents

Sort by: Top

VIBES Project 2021-2025
615 followers
3d · 🔒

Partners unite! The VIBES project gathered at the NIACE Building on May 7th for a dynamic meeting hosted by [Juno Composites Ltd](#). Our consortium delved into progress, sharing achievements, and unveiling future developments. ...see more

You and 17 others 3 comments · 2 reposts

Follower highlights

615
Total followers

303
New followers in the last 365 days

Follower metrics

Highlights

Data for 5/13/2023 - 5/11/2024

1,510
Reactions

25
Comments

53
Reposts

Metrics

Impressions

VIBES Page and Metrics on Facebook

VIBES Page on YouTube

VIBES Project

@vibesproject2291 · 11 subscribers · 3 videos

The VIBES project aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology soluti... >

vibesproject.eu

Subscribe

Home Videos Playlists

Videos

VIBES Summer Course
34 views · 7 months ago

VIBES Project 2021-2025
(with English subtitles)
70 views · 2 years ago

VIBES Project 2021-2025
307 views · 2 years ago

Annex 6. VIBES Fourth Newsletter

Newsletter issue #4

28 June 2023

Welcome to the fourth issue of the VIBES newsletter

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener
Recycling Technology.

Embracing 2 Years of Achievement in Barcelona

Marking the milestone of its 24-month journey, the VIBES project consortium convened in Barcelona, Spain, on the 22nd of June 2023, for a highly productive project meeting, hosted at LEITAT's headquarters. The partners showcased and discussed the remarkable progress and achievements made so far. The meeting also served as an opportune moment to outline the forthcoming semester's plans and future developments. While most participants had the privilege of engaging face-to-face and fostering valuable connections, a few members joined the meeting remotely.

At the heart of the VIBES project lies the ambitious goal of transforming the thermoset composite materials industry, paving the way for their seamless integration into a circular economy. Through the development of innovative technologies and approaches, the project partners strive to establish sustainable and bio-based solutions that enable the reuse of thermoset composites beyond their initial lifecycle. With a budget of nearly 5.3 million Euros and a duration of 48 months, the VIBES project is funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

Technical Developments and Future Steps

Based on the results of the research activities carried out during a period of ten months, in collaboration between AITIIP, LEITAT and SPECIFIC POLYMERS, synergies within and between three reversible approaches of Bio-based Bonding Materials (BBMs) to ease the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components have been investigated: (i) supramolecular, (ii) vitrimers and (iii) Diels-Alder. Two main possible synergies have been identified, in relation to: a) the ability of selectively recycling one material than another, and b) the improvement of the recycling properties of the reversible technology used.

It has been concluded that vitrimer-based BBMs can be selectively degraded thanks to a careful selection of the degradation bath conditions. Significant synergy combining two vitrimer functions, i.e. disulfides and imines, has been observed showing accelerated dynamic exchanges. It has also been demonstrated that two developed approaches, supramolecular and Diels-Alder, could be joined in a single structure and provide a more versatile solution, which should be applied to the fibre instead of directly into the resin system.

In parallel, research has been carried out to improve the stabilisation step and the carbonisation step of lignin-based carbon fibres at both lab scale (ULIM) and semi-pilot scale (DITF). At lab scale, the mechanical properties of the fibres reached the state of the art. The effort will be continued to upscale the lignin-based carbon fibres.

Plasma surface modification of fibres has been studied by LEITAT to promote different effects that can enhance the interfacial adhesion with matrix and/or coupling agents. In addition, new woven fabrics and non-woven mats in natural flax and carbon fibres have been investigated by F&D.

The effect of the new biobased sizing coupling agents, developed by the project, on the hydrophobicity of commercial carbon fibre weaves has been assessed. Furthermore, the production of coated fabrics with the incorporation of the developed supramolecular-based BBMs has been tested. Carbon fibre treatment will be further explored with the biobased resin developed by the project, and optimised.

Using the results of the above research, the next steps will mainly focus on the design, development and validation of new composite materials with intrinsic recyclability properties, followed by the development of the VIBES recycling technology at a pilot scale.

VIBES Presence at Prominent Events

VIBES partners have been actively engaged in various prestigious events, demonstrating their commitment to sustainable innovation.

BCIRCULAR proudly presented VIBES at the Strategic Immersion Day "[Roadmap 2030 for a Sustainable Economy](#)", organized by the LIGHT MOBILITY CLUSTER in Barcelona, Spain. The event provided an ideal platform for showcasing the project's groundbreaking research and its potential impact on the future of mobility. AITIIP, the project's coordinator, showcased their innovative research line, VIBES, at [the eMobility Expo World Congress](#) and at [Wake Up Spain Forum](#). They further extended their reach by participating in [Transfiere 2023](#), in [the "Excellence Forum-Automotive Cluster" conference](#), and a scientific seminar held at [the prestigious International University Menéndez Pelayo](#). To foster knowledge exchange, VIBES coordinator also participated in [a workshop titled "The End of a Product, the Beginning of a Material"](#), emphasising the project's focus on sustainable material usage and circular economy principles.

In addition, Specific Polymers made significant appearances at two important conferences: the "14th Advanced Polymers via Macromolecular Engineering" conference and the EUPOC conference, both held in Italy. Furthermore, F&D actively participated in the 4th International Conference on biobased and biodegradable textiles and polymers in Gent. Similarly, the SAMPE Conference in Belfast served as a platform for the University of Limerick to share their findings and research regarding the production of Carbon Fibres utilizing Lignin as the primary material.

Last but not least, ARCHA actively participated as an exhibitor at the Packaging Première & PCD Milan exhibition, while F&D also took part as an exhibitor at the JEC World 2023 Fair, promoting the VIBES project to industry professionals and attendees.

Through their presence at these notable events, VIBES partners have strengthened their network, shared their expertise, and contributed to the advancement of sustainable practices in the industry.

Publications

The VIBES project has made significant contributions to the scientific community through its research publications. Our partners have published several notable papers in prestigious scientific journals, including the following:

- Guggari, S., Magliozzi, F., Malburet, S., Graillot, A., Destarac, M., & Guerre, M. (2023). [Vanillin-Based Epoxy Vitrimers: Looking at the Cystamine Hardener from a Different Perspective](#). *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 11(15), 6021-6031.
- Malburet, S., Bertrand, H., Richard, C., Lacabanne, C., Dantras, E., & Graillot, A. (2023). [Biobased Epoxy Reactive Diluents Prepared from Monophenol Derivatives: Effect on Viscosity and Glass Transition Temperature of Epoxy Resins](#). *RSC advances*, 13(22), 15099-15106.
- Rubio, M.C, Beaucamp, A, Stróżyk, M.A and Collins, M.N. (2022). [Lignin-Based Carbon Fibres for Green Composites Applications](#). *Encyclopedia of Green Materials*.

The accomplishments of the VIBES project have also been recognised by prominent industrial communication platforms. Our partners were featured in two magazines: [Interempresas' Plastic Channel](#) featuring an interview with BCIRCULAR and [EASY ENGINEERING magazine](#) featuring an interview with AITTIP. These features specifically highlight the innovative research conducted within the project and its potential impact on the industry.

Join us for an unmissable Summer Course

Don't miss the upcoming [VIBES English summer course](#) on “Enhancing Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through Greener Recycling Technology”. This exceptional programme is your chance to acquire the expertise and skills needed to effectively manage and assess information from diverse sources, all while applying it to real-world scenarios. Delve into the fundamental concepts surrounding composite recyclability and witness its practical applications in industries like construction, aeronautics, and naval sectors. By participating in this course, you will not only comprehend the significance of recycling technologies for plastic products but also make a profound impact on the circular economy and overall sustainability.

The VIBES summer course is a 30-hour programme that combines hybrid or blended learning methods. It consists of a 24-hour theoretical component, which will be conducted through AITIIP's e-learning platform, AITEMY (<https://aitemy-learning.com/es/>) and a 6-hour practical part that will take place in person at the headquarters of Teruel Airport (PLATA) in Spain.

Course Availability: The online course is accessible from May 15, 2023, to September 15, 2023, offering flexibility for enrollment and completion at your convenience.

Practical Session: The in-person practical session will be held on September 15, 2023, at PLATA (Teruel Airport) headquarters, located at Polígono de Tiro, 4, 44396 Teruel, Spain.

Create an account and enroll at
<https://aitemy-learning.com/academy/login/index.php>.

[Visit the project's website](#)

Annex 7. VIBES Fifth Newsletter

Newsletter issue #5

11 December 2023

Welcome to the fifth issue of the VIBES newsletter

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener
Recycling Technology.

Montpellier Meet-Up: Unveiling the Latest Developments

Commencing the 30th month of its journey, the collaborative assembly of the VIBES project took place in Montpellier, France, on November 28, 2023. Organised by SPECIFIC POLYMERS, the project meeting proved to be exceptionally fruitful. Partners gathered to present and discuss the significant strides and accomplishments achieved thus far. Additionally, the meeting provided an opportune platform to outline plans for the upcoming semester and discuss future developments. Although many participants enjoyed the privilege of in-person engagement and the opportunity to build valuable connections, a few members joined the meeting remotely.

The core objective of the VIBES project is to revolutionise the thermoset composites industry, facilitating their incorporation into a circular economy. The project partners aim to achieve this ambitious goal by developing innovative technologies and approaches, working towards sustainable and biobased solutions that allow for the reuse of thermoset composite materials beyond their initial lifecycle. Funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, the VIBES project boasts a budget of nearly 5.3 million Euros and is set to span 48 months.

Exploring technical developments and future strategies in the 1st Roundtable with stakeholders

The VIBES project achieved a significant milestone by hosting its first roundtable on November 29th, 2023, in Montpellier and in hybrid mode, moderated by Q-PLAN. [This meeting brought together key project partners and crucial stakeholders, members of the VIBES Stakeholders' Board.](#) Having received feedback from stakeholder representatives on the project's progress and results, we present an overview of our accomplishments since the beginning of the project.

The VIBES project outlines a solution involving the development of Biobased Bonding Materials (BBMs) with controlled reversible properties. In the initial phase, VIBES focused on screening chemistries to identify potential BBMs. Following this, the spotlight was on exploring synergies between reversible technologies, especially in the binding between resins and fibres. The outcomes of this process were 18 BBMs compatible with targeted resins and fibres. The subsequent step was centred around the upscaling of the most promising BBMs, involving the successful synthesis of 1kg of the best BBM to be further utilised for thermoset composites development. The strategy employed by VIBES emphasised the use of BBMs as biobased chemical moieties capable of decomposing under specific external stimuli, facilitating the separation between the matrix and the reinforcing material for efficient recycling. The overview encompassed various resin types, such as epoxy resins (for aeronautical, construction, and marine applications), vinyl ester resins (for construction), and unsaturated polyester resins (for marine), along with bio-carbon and flax fibres (as reinforcing materials).

The project's advancements also included the successful creation of two generations of substitute resins which are being processed very well based on their complete characterisation, and the production of carbon fibres from waste form forestry industry with enhanced mechanical performance. Yet another advancement was the application of surface treatments to activate various fibres and the introduction of new fabrics, emphasising the exploration of suitable flax and biobased carbon fibre weaves for high-performance composite materials.

In particular, the following have been achieved during the last six months of the project. Including BBMs, resins and fibres, and putting them together in several combinations (either carbon, glass or flax fibres with resins), VIBES proceeded with several methods for producing thermoset composites. The produced thermoset composites are addressing engineering applications in three different sectors and will be validated based on their specific requirements, specifically for the construction, aeronautics and marine sectors. The marine sector application exhibited properties surpassing requirements, presenting a highly promising solution. Meanwhile, the construction and aeronautical sector applications achieved positive results with certain challenges identified, slated for further improvement in the upcoming project activities, in particular for improving gel time issues and interlaminar shear strength.

VIBES Presence at Prominent Events

VIBES partners have been actively engaged in recent events, showcasing their cutting-edge research in recycling technologies for composite materials.

AITIIP, our coordinator, made notable appearances at the [Polymer Connect 2023](#), [1st IPPT_TWINN conference](#), and the Packnet conference "Circular Innovation in Packaging: the road to a sustainable future". Over the past six months, LEITAT participated in the [Global Fiber Congress 2023](#), while PLATA joined the "Advances and Development of the Aeronautical and Aerospace Sector" conference by Antonio Gargallo University Foundation, highlighting the impactful strides within the VIBES project. More recently, ARCHA took centre stage at the [ECOMONDO FAIR 2023](#), presenting VIBES' research and innovation activities.

VIBES Summer Course Concluded

On September 15, 2023, VIBES proudly concluded its enriching Summer Course on "Enhancing Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through Greener Recycling Technology" with a dynamic 6-hour hands-on session at PLATA's facilities. The course seamlessly blended a comprehensive 24-hour theoretical module on AITIIP's e-learning platform, AITEMY, covering crucial aspects such as the design and development of circular economy strategies for thermoset composites, the significance of biobased and improved fibres, and practical applications in industry and scaling up.

Our innovative blended learning approach empowered participants to navigate through asynchronous modules at their own pace while immersing themselves in valuable industry insights during in-person sessions.

Watch now the success of this transformative experience in our latest video: <https://t.ly/A-6nV>

Publications

The VIBES project has made significant contributions to the scientific community through its research publications. Our partners have published one more paper in a prestigious scientific journal:

Vidal, J., Hornero, C., Garcia, R., Cuartero, J., Beaucamp, A., Collins, M.N, Garcia, L., Ponce D., Royo, M.C, Sanchez E., Castell, P. [Use of covalent dynamic networks as binders on epoxy-based carbon fiber composites: Effect on properties, processing, and recyclability.](#) Polym Compos. 2023; 44(11): 7444-7456.

Amplifying impact through synergies with new sister projects

To promote collaboration and knowledge exchange, while also achieving a more efficient and effective use of resources, VIBES has established three new synergies including [CUBIC](#), [EoLO-HUBS](#) and [BIO-UPTAKE](#) projects.

What's next?

The upcoming phases will primarily concentrate on evaluating the debonding pre-treatment of the developed thermoset composite materials and exploring the use of green solvents for recycling their components. Subsequently, the focus will shift towards advancing the VIBES recycling technology to pilot scale. Additionally, three distinct business models will be developed for the exploitation of key project results, utilising the business canvas model.

[Visit the project's website](#)

ANNEX 8. VIBES Fifth Press Release

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu
VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

PRESS RELEASE

29/06/2023

VIBES: Embracing 2 Years of Achievement in Barcelona

Celebrating their 2-year milestone, the VIBES project consortium gathered in Barcelona, Spain, on June 22, 2023, for an impactful project meeting held at LEITAT's premises. The meeting proved to be highly productive, with partners showcasing and discussing the remarkable progress and achievements attained thus far. It also provided an ideal platform to outline future plans and upcoming developments for the next semester.

VIBES is centred around revolutionising the thermoset composite materials industry, aiming to seamlessly integrate them into a circular economy. With a budget of nearly 5.3 million Euros and a duration of 48 months, the project is funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190.

The project partners have made significant progress in developing bio-based bonding materials (BBMs) for thermoset composites. Working together, the project research team explored synergies in three reversible approaches of BBMs: supramolecular, vitrimers, and Diels-Alder. These research efforts identified potential synergies in the ability of selectively recycling one material than another and the improvement of the recycling properties of the reversible technology used. The project also focused on improving the stabilisation and carbonisation steps of lignin-based carbon fibres, achieving outstanding mechanical properties at lab scale. Additionally, plasma surface modification of fibres was explored, and new fabrics in natural flax and carbon fibres were investigated. Carbon fibre treatment will be further explored with the biobased resin developed by the project, and optimised. Moving forward, the project aims to design, develop, and validate new composite materials with intrinsic recyclability properties, followed by the pilot-scale development of VIBES recycling technology.

Throughout their journey, the partners actively participated in prominent events, expanding their reach and impact. From presentations at conferences like "Roadmap 2030 for a Sustainable Economy" to exhibiting at exhibitions such as Packaging Première & PCD Milan and JEC World 2023 Fair, partners strengthened their network and shared their expertise in sustainable innovation.

The VIBES project's research contributions have also been recognized through publications in prestigious scientific journals. Notable papers include topics such as lignin-based carbon fibres and biobased epoxy reactive diluents. Additionally, industrial communication platforms featured interviews with project partners, showcasing the project's innovative research and its potential industry impact.

To further exchange knowledge, the VIBES project is offering an English summer course on "Enhancing Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through Greener Recycling Technology." This 30-hour program combines theoretical and practical components, providing participants with expertise and skills to apply real-world scenarios in the circular economy. The VIBES summer course is accessible online from May 15, 2023, to September 15, 2023, with a practical session held on September 15, 2023, at PLATA (Teruel Airport) headquarters in Spain. Interested participants can create an account and enroll at <https://aitemy-learning.com/academy/login/index.php>.

Stay informed about the latest progress and developments of the VIBES project by visiting the official website at www.vibesproject.eu. Don't forget to subscribe to their newsletter for regular updates and follow VIBES on social media to stay connected.

Disclaimer

This press release reflects only the author's view, and the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ANNEX 9. VIBES Sixth Press Release

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu
VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

PRESS RELEASE

18/12/2023

VIBES Attains Milestone with Successful Roundtable Event in Montpellier

Commencing the 30th month of its journey, the 6th project meeting of VIBES project took place in Montpellier, France, on November 28, 2023. Organised by SPECIFIC POLYMERS, the meeting proved to be exceptionally fruitful. Partners gathered to present and discuss the significant strides and accomplishments achieved thus far.

On November 29th, the project reached another pivotal moment with its 1st roundtable, held in Montpellier in a hybrid format and expertly moderated by Q-PLAN. This roundtable united key project partners and crucial stakeholders, including members of the VIBES Stakeholders' Board, providing invaluable feedback on progress and results.

At the core of VIBES lies the mission to transform the thermoset composite materials industry, strategically incorporating them into a circular economy framework. With a budget of nearly 5.3 million Euros and a duration of 48 months, the project is funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190.

The project partners have made significant progress in developing thermoset composites with intrinsic recycling properties, using several methods and combinations of bio-based materials, including biobased

bonding materials (BBMs), bio-based resins and fibres (either bio-based carbon fibres or flax fibres). The developed thermoset composites are addressing engineering applications in three different industrial sectors and will be validated based on their requirements, specifically for the construction, aeronautics and marine sectors. The marine sector application exhibited properties surpassing requirements, presenting a highly promising solution. Meanwhile, the construction and aeronautical sector applications achieved positive results with certain challenges identified, slated for further improvement in the upcoming project activities, in particular for improving gel time issues and interlaminar shear strength.

Engaging actively in significant events, our partners extended their influence and broadened their impact in various forums. The project developments were showcased at key industry events including Polymer Connect 2023, 1st IPPT_TWINN conference, and Packnet conference "Circular Innovation in Packaging: the road to a sustainable future". Additionally, active participation in the Global Fiber Congress 2023, the "Advances and Development of the Aeronautical and Aerospace Sector" conference and the ECOMONDO FAIR 2023 highlighted VIBES' impactful strides.

VIBES wrapped up its impactful Summer Course on September 15, 2023, focusing on enhancing recyclability of thermoset composites. The 24-hour theoretical module covered circular economy strategies, biobased fibres, and practical industry applications. Our unique blended learning empowered participants, offering flexibility and industry insights. Watch the success unfold in our latest video: <https://t.ly/A-6nV>

Stay informed about the latest progress and developments of the VIBES project by visiting the official website at www.vibesproject.eu. Don't forget to subscribe to their newsletter for regular updates and follow VIBES on social media to stay connected.

Disclaimer

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Annex 10. Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template

The form below has been designed to help keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activities of the project. As a reminder, communication and dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, conferences, fairs, forums, workshops, roundtables, press releases, newsletters, publications, presentations etc. Please, complete ANY RELEVANT PARTS of the form below each time you perform a communication or dissemination activity, either small or large.																
Partner name																
No.	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity	Title of publication (journal, newspaper etc.) or event (conference, workshop, training, roundtable, info-day, exhibition, TV programme etc.)	Title of article (scientific, press release, news etc.) or presentation given by the partner	Type of audience	Size of audience (inc. of persons per type of audience)	Language used/ countries reached out	Role and description of partner organisation's involvement <i>(e.g. facilitator,</i>	Type of project promotional material used <i>(e.g.</i> <i>leaflets, infographic,</i> <i>poster or infographic</i> <i>roll-ups etc.)</i>	Quantity of project promotional material handed out <i>(inc. of copies</i> <i>distributed per type of</i> <i>material)</i>	Name of other VIBES partners or external organisations responsible / involved	Short description of the activity	Evidence: URL, screenshot, photo (given that the target group has given its consent)	Significant contacts made (name, position, organisation; if consent, to store and share email address, telephone)	Other comments
1																
2																
3																

Annex 11. News Reporting Template

News about Project Developments

Picture (if available)	
Title	
News (main content)	
Key words/ hashtags (for social media)	

Attachments

Please attach any relevant pictures/ images as separate jpg files with as high resolution as possible.

Annex 12. Event Reporting Form

Event’s Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organisers	
Audience (number and type, including % of female attendees)	
Duration	

Event’s goals, objectives and relevance to VIBES

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc). Was the event relevant to VIBES? To what extent?

Organisation of the event

This section is completed only in case of organising a project event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

How was the event/activity organised?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Promotional activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the VIBES project promoted during the event?

Structure of the event

Description of the event’s sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observation that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

Annexes: Attachments

If applicable, the following Annexes should be attached:

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if applicable)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g. leaflets, infographic, newsletters etc.)

Annex 13. External Conferences and Events Template

		Identified External Conferences and Events							
No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Date	Location	Registration fees	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission etc)	Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)	Website	Added by (Partner)
1									
2									
3									